

**Examining international leadership practices to promote a positive
research culture in Higher Education Institutes**

**MBA Educational Leadership (International)
Dissertation**

Seán Lacey, BSc, PhD

**Supervised by
Jennifer J. Wilkinson, BA, MBA**

12 September 2022

Word Count: 21,981 words

This dissertation may be made available to the general public for borrowing, photocopying or consultation without the prior consent of the author.

For

Eilís, Aoibhe & Ciarán

Acknowledgements

First and foremost, I would like to thank my wife, Eilís, and children, Aoibhe and Ciarán, for your unwavering and tremendous support, and belief in me throughout my MBA studies. Completing this would not have been possible without the three of you. Thank you!

I would like to express my thanks to my supervisor, Ms Jennifer Wilkinson, for your indispensable advice, continuous support, and guidance during the dissertation. Your attention to detail is impeccable.

Thank you to Dr Trevor Male, Dr Domini Bingham and Prof. Peter Earley for your support, advice and direction throughout the entire MBA programme.

Thank you also to Dr Stephen Cassidy, Dr David Goulding and Dr Áine Ní Shé who encouraged me to do an MBA.

Finally, a big thank you to the senior research leaders who agreed to participate in my research study. The wealth of experience and knowledge that you shared with me was invaluable.

Abstract

In Higher Education Institutes (HEIs) there is a growing emphasis on promoting good research practices in all aspects of research, from fundamental research to applied research to commercialisation. This study examines international leadership practices to promote a positive research culture in HEIs in terms of types of leadership models senior research leaders find are most effective, along with the practices they have found to be most impactful in leading change.

The research design was constructed using semi-structured interviews with five senior research leaders. Countries that were members of the European Network of Research Integrity Offices (ENRIO), with HEIs that were members of the European Association of Research Management and Administration (EARMA) were used as part of the sample selection process. With the topic being under-researched, the examination was kept as a small-scale exploratory study using opportunistic and purposive sampling to recruit participants. Data analysis was carried out using NVivo.

Findings from the research study showed that the overarching leadership style to promote a positive research culture within HEIs was collective, with adaptive and competent boundary spanning characteristics, along with cognisance of the need for continuous professional development. There was agreement among all participants that change in the research culture is occurring, and leaders need to adapt to these changes. Findings also outlined that in order for HEIs to be proactive as opposed to reactive to change, evidenced-based research in collaboration with the future users is essential, requiring support from management in resourcing the appropriate infrastructure and training. Furthermore, findings suggested that HEI values and principles need first to be agreed and then subsequently complemented by the necessary policies and training at the various levels within the HEI. Research integrity and open research were seen as integral components to promoting a positive research culture in HEIs.

Table of Contents

List of Tables	v
List of Figures	v
List of Abbreviations	vi
1. Introduction	1
2. Literature Review	5
System Leadership in Higher Education	6
Professional Development to Promote a Positive Research Culture	11
Pressures and Challenges in Research Culture Leadership	14
Summary	21
3. Methodology	23
Research Paradigms and Study Type	23
Research Instrument, Method and Timeframe	24
Sampling Method	26
Ethical Considerations	28
Data Collection	32
Data Analysis	33
Evaluations of the Methodology	37
Summary	39
4. Overview of Findings	40
Participant Attributes	40
Codes and Themes	41
Research Questions and Hypotheses	44
Summary	45
5. Discussion	46
Leadership Practices and Culture Change	46
Infrastructure, Training and Support in RI	50
Research and Professional Development in RI	51
Open Research Practices	53

External Engagements	54
Research Misconduct, QRPs and Compliance	56
Reforming Research Assessment.....	57
Summary	59
6. Conclusions and Future Work	60
Research Questions and Hypotheses	60
Limitations of the Research	61
Recommendations for Future Research	62
Closing Remarks.....	62
References.....	64
Appendices	76
Appendix i. Initial Interview Schedule.....	76
Appendix ii. Ethics Approval Letter.....	78
Appendix iii. Information Leaflet.....	79
Appendix iv. Consent Form	82
Appendix v. Research Data Management Plan.....	83
Appendix vi. RStudio Script for Figures	90
Appendix vii. Word Frequency Analysis Results.....	92
Appendix viii. Mapping of Codes to Themes.....	93

List of Tables

Table 4.1 Demographic attributes of participants.....	40
Table 4.2 Summary of number of code contributions and references per participant.	41
Table A.1 Initial word frequency analysis of most frequently occurring words, with a weighted percentage of at least 0.5%.	92
Table A.2 Word frequency analysis with stop-words approach implemented.	92
Table A.3 Mapping of collated codes, using axial coding, to overarching themes.....	93

List of Figures

Figure 4.1 Summary of initial input from participants when asked the question “What do you consider to be good research practice?”	42
Figure 4.2 Initial word frequency analysis of most frequently occurring words, with a weighted percentage of at least 0.5%.	43
Figure 4.3 Word frequency analysis with stop-words approach implemented.	43
Figure 4.4 Overarching themes from the semi-structured interviews complemented with the number of references to each theme.....	44
Figure 5.5 Strategy for Culture Change (Nosek, 2019).	51

List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
CRedit	Contributor Roles Taxonomy
CV	Curriculum Vitae
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DORA	Declaration on Research Assessment
EARMA	European Association of Research Management and Administration
ENRIO	European Network of Research Integrity Offices
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
FFP	Fabrication, Falsification and Plagiarism
HE	Higher Education
HEI	Higher Education Institute
HKP	Hong Kong Principles
ISBN	International Standard Book Number
JPD	Joint Practice Development
MBA	Master of Business Administration
No.	Number
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OR	Open Research
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
PLC	Professional Learning Community
QRP	Questionable Research Practice
RCR	Responsible Conduct of Research
RE	Research Ethics
RI	Research Integrity
RIPP	Research Integrity Promotion Plan
SOPs4RI	Standard Operating Procedures for Research Integrity
TU	Technological University
UCL	University College London
UK	United Kingdom
USA	United States of America

1. Introduction

In Higher Education Institutes (HEIs) there is a growing emphasis on promoting good research practices in all aspects of research, from undergraduate studies to postgraduate studies to studies with industry (All European Academies, 2017; National Research Integrity Forum, 2019; Science Europe, 2022). Research integrity (RI) underpins research activity and excellence, and is considered a critical component of the basis for researchers to trust each other as well as the research record (Science Europe, 2015). National Research Integrity Forum (2019) define RI as relating:

...to the performance of research to the highest standards of professionalism and rigour, and to the accuracy and trustworthiness of the research record in publications and elsewhere. (p.3.)

There are however instances when research ethics (RE) and RI are used interchangeably, while for the purposes of this dissertation, RE and RI have overlapping themes, but are not one in the same. RE is focussed on “doing research with responsibility, particularly towards participants, colleagues, employers, funders and society” (Carling, 2019, p.4), while RI is the principles and practices of good research (All European Academies, 2017).

The motivation for the dissertation topic was initially based on the Irish research landscape and changes within it, in response to shifting requirements by funding agencies - e.g. Irish Research Council, Science Foundation Ireland, Enterprise Ireland and Health Research Board - if RI policies and procedures are not in place (Research Prioritisation Steering Group, 2018; Irish University Association, 2021). The position in Ireland is very much led by emerging requirements and practice internationally (European Commission et al., 2020; Horizon Europe, 2021; Science Europe, 2022) and the national positions on RI and the general organisation of research. The national and international research landscapes are explored further in the literature review, including the recently published framework for reforming research assessment by Science Europe et al. (2022).

In recent years, in parallel with the importance of RI, there is a growing emphasis being placed on open research (OR) (Higher Education Authority, 2020; Science Europe, 2021). OR, Open Scholarship and Open Science are terms that are used reciprocally and relate to collaborative ways of generating, communicating and sharing research findings as early as possible in the research

lifecycle (National Open Research Forum, 2019; European Commission, 2019). For the dissertation, the term OR will be used, which overarchingly incorporates openness of results, data, protocols and others aspects of the research process (European Commission et al., 2020). In the planning of the dissertation, and subsequent research questions, OR was not in the scope for the dissertation, but has been included as it is an evolving field with growing importance in terms of promoting a positive research culture in HEIs (Science Europe, 2022). Although, RI and OR have overlapping themes, they are individually well-defined in that RI focusses on the conduct of research, while OR focusses on the dissemination of research, with both being attributes of embedding good research practice in a research culture (Haven et al., 2022).

Some of the key challenges when embedding good research practices in the research culture of a HEI are around having the necessary infrastructure and resources (Wilkinson et al., 2016; Haven et al., 2022), along with the appropriate buy-in from management (Mejlgaard et al., 2020; Science Europe, 2022). Furthermore, there is the issue around the interpretation of good research practice which is often dependent on the research context, collaborators involved and may vary across disciplines (Mårtensson et al., 2016; National Research Integrity Forum, 2022). With challenges, there are opportunities, and in the case of RI and opportunities, this is around research that is carried out with transparency and accountability, thus ensuring trust by the wider community (Science Europe, 2015; Robishaw et al, 2019). The research landscape is constantly shifting (Mowles et al., 2018; World Economic Forum, 2019), with leadership promoting a positive research culture being an emerging field, with minimal research to date. The dissertation seeks to fill a gap in understanding international interpretations of good research practice and the conditions under which it can thrive, in order to contribute to the field.

There are numerous examples of good research practice (Räsänen and Moore, 2016; Moher et al. 2020), along with guidance as to what is expected of leaders to promote these practices (Evans et al, 2022; Horbach et al., 2022) However in order to align with policies and procedures in relation to good research practice there is often a culture change required, where the incentives and rewards for investing in such a culture change are not always recognised (European Commission et al., 2020; United States Government Accountability Office, 2022). Mejlgaard et al. (2020) and Labib et al. (2022) state that in order to progress the RI agenda, there are actions and compliance needed

around support, organisation and communication for research and for this to be achieved, strong leadership is required.

There are examples in the literature of where leadership in RI is to the fore, along with steps required to foster a culture of RI within a HEI (Forsberg et al., 2018; Casci and Adams, 2020), but there is little discussion of successful leadership models or approaches to enable this promotion. Senge et al. (2014) state that “the deep changes necessary to accelerate progress against society’s most intractable problems require a unique type of leader – the system leader, a person who catalyses collective leadership” (p.1). The definition of a “system” is “a complex whole; a set of things working together as a mechanism or interconnecting network” (Oxford Dictionary, 2011). In the HEI context, a system is not only due to physical dispersion (e.g., multiple campuses), but within a campus there may be multiple units from faculties to schools to departments, where each unit needs to maintain its own identity and distinctiveness (Weick, 1976). Ham (2015) states:

Unlike successful organisational leaders, [system leaders] are distinguished by their experience of working across services and organisations, almost invariably in circumstances of considerable complexity. The challenge they faced was how to build relationships with others to improve outcomes for the populations they served. (p.3.)

If HEIs are considered as systems and a whole-system approach is needed to accelerate change (Senge et al., 2014), it can therefore be purported that in order to drive successful organisational change with RI throughout the research culture, system leadership may be an appropriate model.

Successful leadership models depend on the journey the system is on (House and Mitchell, 1974; Muczyk and Reimann, 1987). The dissertation explores various leadership models within the system leadership field, from directive leadership (House, 1971) to collective leadership (Senge et al., 2014). It also explores the need to be adaptive (Heifetz et al., 2004), advocates of professional development (Stoll et al., 2012) and possess an awareness of competent boundary spanning (Williams, 2002) when working across systems. In parallel with these leadership models and given the ever-changing research landscape (Mowles et al., 2018; World Economic Forum, 2019), the need to be forward thinking and prepared for change (Kotter, 1996) is explored. Throughout the dissertation, these leadership models and approaches are related to the currently emerging RI agenda.

With educational leadership in RI being an emerging area, the dissertation aims to examine the leadership practices, in relation to implementing RI policies and procedures, to establish effective approaches to promoting a positive research culture in HEIs. From semi-structured interviews with senior research leaders across an opportunistic and purposive sample of HEIs in Europe, the objective was to collate examples of leadership practices that have been successful, along with leadership practices that did not realise their potential, in underpinning a positive research culture in respective HEIs. Seeking to answer the questions “What type of leadership models do senior research leaders find most effective in promoting a positive research culture in HEIs?” and “What practices have senior research leaders found most effective in leading change and promoting a positive research culture in their HEI, in line with changing internal and external requirements?” the study aims to provide insights that may contribute to establishing evidence informed recommendations on leadership practices of RI to promote a positive research culture in HEIs. A longer-term goal is that the dissertation may form initial steps to support HEIs’ development of leadership in RI training and strategy in future.

2. Literature Review

There are multiple facets to a positive research culture in HEIs (Forsberg et al., 2018; Casci and Adams, 2020; Ayres, 2021), along with a multitude of successful leadership practices (House and Mitchell, 1974; Kania and Kramer, 2011; Senge et al., 2014), however there is little evidence of leadership practices to promote a positive research culture in HEIs. This chapter takes a proportion of the literature available on leadership practices that may be mapped to a research culture setting, while examining the current research policy and practitioner contexts (All European Academies, 2017; National Research Integrity Forum, 2019; Science Europe, 2022). With the changing research landscape (Mowles et al., 2018; World Economic Forum, 2019), literature across leadership theory that promotes and encourages adaption and learning (Heifetz et al., 2004; Stoll et al., 2012; Kools and Stoll, 2016) within a system is discussed.

A stepwise approach was adopted to distil literature available for the dissertation. Initially the literature was isolated using two methods.

1. This research is part fulfilment of an MBA Educational Leadership (International) therefore applicable literature introduced in the programme has been utilised.
2. Between February and September 2022 the British Educational Index, Education Resources Information Center, Google Scholar and ScienceDirect were used to search for the keywords: system/collective/adaptive leadership; research integrity; research culture; higher education. AdvanceHE, the European Commission, Nature, Science Europe and Science Foundation Ireland were also searched for national and international RI policy and practitioner contexts.

Literature searches were refined based on language being English and countries typically being in Europe and North America. Dates of publications were predominantly the past twenty years, although there were a few older studies based on that literature being seminal work in the area. Finally, while the dissertation's focus is tertiary education, there are references to literature from primary and secondary education settings where findings are applicable.

Based on the findings from the literature review, the chapter concludes with stating the study's research questions and hypotheses.

System Leadership in Higher Education

In the HEI context a system is appropriate when considering Oxford Dictionary's (2011) definition of a system as "a complex whole; a set of things working together as a mechanism or interconnecting network". HEIs may not only be multi-campus, but within campuses there may be multiple academic units, where each unit needs to maintain its own identity and distinctiveness, but also conform to an overarching HEI position or strategy (Weick, 1976). It follows that system leadership should therefore be appropriate when focussing on the dissertation's primary research question of: What type of leadership models do senior research leaders adopt to promote a positive research culture in their HEI?

Successful leadership styles are dependent on the journey the system is on (House and Mitchell, 1974; Muczyk and Reimann, 1987). In terms of promoting a positive research culture within HEIs, which are large complex organisations that often have challenges around physical and digital connectedness (Mowles et al., 2018; Technological Universities Research Network, 2019; Kilpert et al., 2022), multiple leadership styles should be required. The following sections explore these leadership styles in more detail, relating them to the currently emerging RI agenda.

One type of system leadership is directive leadership (Muczyk and Reimann, 1987), where House (1971) states that that directive leadership starts with a clear goal being targeted. In terms of clear instruction and direction to motivate a system, Leithwood (1994), Hallinger and Heck (1997) and Hallinger (2005) advocate for an instructional and directive leadership model to consolidate the performance of effectiveness and output. While these scholars are focussed on pre-tertiary education there are broad generalisations across all education systems. These authors posit that the wider community are motivated by the leader to change, with clear instruction underpinned by a mission, which impacts the overall culture of the system. Although directive leadership may seem fitting in the context of promoting a positive research culture within a HEI, a study by Faraci et al. (2013) including 299 managers measuring leaders' judgments and preferred styles found there is a fine balance between successful directive leadership

and one that generates low-self-esteem, lack of initiative, creativity and independence. Taking Faraci et al.'s (2013) finding, with the focus of the dissertation being on leadership practices that promote a positive research culture, while directive leadership may be a starting point it would not seem to be the ideal leadership model for sustainability within a system.

Murphy et al. (2006) state:

Leadership is a process; it is not a personal trait or characteristic of an individual...Leadership involves influence; it requires interactions and relationships among people...Leadership involves purpose; it helps organizations and the people affiliated with them move toward reaching desired goals. (p.3.)

Murphy et al.'s (2006) definition of leadership posits that leadership can be shared among multiple stakeholders with clear relationships between its leaders and wider community. This is important in a research context where in Hanover Research's (2014) work on recommended practices for building a research culture, they found that establishing congenial relationships among researchers to be a key institutional characteristic that facilitates research productivity and has a positive impact on the overarching research culture.

Directive leadership appears to go against the definition of leadership by Murphy et al. (2006), which leverages interactions, relationships and leans towards working together and being collective. Muczyk and Reimann (1987) state that directive leadership has its place, but a leader's positionality can adapt and change over time, while Kania and Kramer (2011) advocate for working collaboratively and collectively with others on a common agenda as being a key to the success and sustainability of a system over time. Internationally in a research context, in Hanover Research' (2014) found that creating opportunities for collaboration in research was a positive influential factor for the research culture. Nationally, in 2019 an Irish government-led report was published that provided a significant examination of Irish Technological Universities (TUs) and what is required of them to achieve sectorial and national strategic objectives. To the fore of the many recommendations was the requirement that TUs "enhance[e] opportunities for learners, employers and society ... with a particular focus on industry collaboration and innovation" (Technological Universities Research Network, 2019, p.vii). Leadership with industry collaborations comes with

challenges in terms of RI, with National Research Integrity Forum (2022) publishing guidance for researchers on how to reinforce a culture of RI in collaborations. National Research Integrity Forum (2022), based on input and expertise from a collective of HEI research leaders, state the need to have conversations from the outset on the responsibilities of all partners while acknowledging different research practices across disciplines and cultures. In order to maintain a responsible conduct of research (RCR), Hanover Research (2014) posit an assertive, participative style of leadership when building a culture of research and one that engages across functions to ensure consistency in approach to RI.

Hanover Research's (2014) posit on leadership is analogous to Senge et al.'s (2014) broad ranging work on collective leadership which highlights the importance of collaborating with other system leaders to ensure consistency. Within a HEI there may be many sub-functions – Departments within Schools; Schools with Faculties; Faculties within Campuses; Campuses within the HEI – that all wish to be distinct but are required to comply with a core set of values, policies and procedures analogous to a coupled system (Weick, 1976; Orton and Weick, 1990). Senge et al. (2014) advocate for being proactive as opposed to reactive when it comes to growing for the future by developing conditions that are sustainable and lead to change in the long run. They follow this with the need to allow time to reflect and have group conversations on potential changes required within a system, while ensuring that the group conversations contain a mix of expertise across disciplines, especially if dealing with a potentially loosely coupled system.

Weick (1976) states that loose coupling is a situation where one entity is responsive but yet retains levels of separateness and identity. It is important to note, although a seminal theory and updated in Orton and Weick (1990), Weick's (1976) work was based in a different era of Higher Education (HE). Singh (2001), Mowles et al. (2018) and World Economic Forum (2019) point out that what is expected of HEIs has changed immensely in recent years, with HE's expected impact of its research on societal change, engagement with industry and other related areas. In a study of research culture in the University of Glasgow, Casci and Adams (2020) state that inconsistency in approach to embedding RI across units has a negative impact on the research culture. Elken and Vukasovic (2019) state that more contemporary data in terms of loose coupling in HE research is required. Based on a study of over 40 years of literature across broad range of 209 articles and a qualitative review of 22 articles, Elken and Vukasovic (2019) found a wide and varied approach to the

interpretation of loose coupling and suggest “to revisit what loose coupling in higher education really entails, both in conceptual and empirical terms” (p.16). However, irrespective of the use of the term loose coupling, Elken and Vukasovic (2019) found that within HEIs multiple couplings do co-exist, often with a complex co-existence within the system. Hence, for the purposes of promoting a research culture, leadership that is aware of potential coupling and methods to overcome challenges are important, and if a system is truly a system then there needs to be evidence of cohesiveness (Weick, 1976; Orton and Weick, 1990).

According to Kania and Kramer (2011) a system should change collectively. In order to maintain the appropriate levels of responsiveness, distinctness and coupling the importance of competent boundary spanners and boundary spanning leadership should be to the fore (Williams, 2002). Although, Williams’ (2002) work was framed within the UK public policy context, there are learnings from the findings in that when working across boundaries, the boundary spanner leader encourages collaboration, facilitates meetings of stakeholders and provides the catalyst to start action. In a qualitative study on one UK HEI, Pryor and Henley (2018) found that stakeholder engagement and engaging “horizontally” across academic units are two prevalent boundaries to overcome in a HE setting that aims to form a strategic response to pressures facing the sector. Although the finding is interesting and some way translational for the dissertation, a key limitation is the sample size is only one HEI, which may suggest that further research is required for the findings to be generalisable.

Wellcome Trust (2020) carried out a large study using interviews, workshops and an online survey to determine what was the researcher perception of the culture they worked in. 4,267 researchers completed the survey that contained up to 70 questions. One of the questions was “What does good [research] culture look like?”, with one of eight most common responses being where “leadership is transparent and open” (p.48). Trust was another leading response Wellcome Trust’s (2020) survey results, which aligns with Science Europe’s (2015) statement that RI is the basis for researchers to trust each other as well as the research record. Science Europe’s (2015) briefing paper investigated the efforts to address issues of RI and found when trying to create a culture of RI, a key factor was to create a supportive environment for all researchers, from academics to administrators to librarians to technicians and contract researchers.

The above findings are suggestive of a collective leadership approach. Leithwood et al. (2008) outlines four domains, Kania and Kramer (2011) has five conditions, while Senge et al. (2014) state three core principles that enable successful leadership which are all underpinned by openness, communication and trust. Although Leithwood et al.'s (2008) findings were based on an overview of literature on successful school leadership, while Kania and Kramer (2011) and Senge et al.'s (2014) findings relate to large organisational settings, the overarching understanding of openness, communication and trust in leadership translates to the focus of this research study.

In Leithwood et al. (2008), Kania and Kramer (2011) and Senge et al.'s (2014) domains, conditions and principles respectively, all are interrelated and speak to each other with another very clear characteristic in leadership: being able to adapt. Singh (2001) and Mowles et al. (2018) share the view that when it comes to the HE landscapes, there are continuous changes. Based on over 40 interviews with leaders in UK HEIs, Mowles et al. (2018) found that the changes are wide and varied from influences from external agencies, national and international policies, organisational structures to stakeholder engagement. Singh's (2001) overview of the literature relating to HE transformations found that:

The strategic routes to being able to re-appropriate a broader notion of higher education have to be identified and the agencies and resources that can give effect to such a notion have to be drawn in. (p.10.)

The changes alluded to by Singh (2001) may be technical problems that are well-defined with known solutions, equally the changes may be adaptive problems that are well-defined but with unknown solutions (Heifetz et al., 2004). In terms of research culture, the pressures around high standards nationally and internationally in research can be technical or adaptive problems which may originate from internal HEI policy and procedures, along with expectation from external funding agencies. Nationally and internationally, HEIs will be excluded from future funding applications by funding agencies if policies and procedures relating to RI and good research practice are not in place (Research Prioritisation Steering Group, 2018; Irish University Association, 2021; Horizon Europe, 2021). Compliance with these policies and procedures ultimately have a knock-on effect to promoting a positive research culture within HEIs and what is expected of senior research leaders in order to realise this. In terms of overcoming these potential technical and adaptive RI problems, a leader with adaptive traits would appear to be essential within a system (Heifetz et al., 2004).

In parallel with pressures and expectations from both national and international funding agencies, teaching and learning, research and scholarship, and engagement are the main pillars for HEIs in Ireland (Department of Education and Skills, 2011). With these pillars, there is a growing requirement to ensure good research practices in all aspects of research from fundamental research to applied research to commercialisation across all these pillars (National Research Integrity Forum, 2019). Furthermore, Technological Universities Research Network (2019) stated what is required of TUs to achieve sectorial and national strategic objectives, along with what is expected of them in terms of leadership in that:

TUs will be the national leaders for building strong cultures of research and postgraduate education for the technological sector. TUs will need to raise the level of their research and innovation capacity substantially to achieve these targets. (p.27.)

Returning to educational leadership literature, an OECD report by Kools and Stoll (2016) based on a review of schools as learning organisations, states that a leader should have the capacity to present a problem in an understandable manner, with the relevant stakeholders understanding the challenges ahead, but equally the opportunities that may be realised once the challenge is overcome. Kools and Stoll's (2016) report shows how aligned a successful system is with being a learning organisation, with a leader that can adapt also being one who is open to the importance of professional development. Given how a leader promoting a positive research culture has to adapt to internal and external influences (Singh, 2001; Mowles et al., 2018), then that leader needs to be open to being an active learner and engaging in professional development (Easton, 2008).

Professional Development to Promote a Positive Research Culture

Casci and Adams (2020) wrote about the practices they have used in the University of Glasgow to foster a positive research culture through “develop[ing] policies, guidance, communications, training and related initiatives that support the success of researchers at all stages of their career” (p.1). However, they follow this with stating that developing policy is not enough, researchers should be shown how to implement and make practical changes to their research practices. Of course, Casci and Adams (2020) was based on the learning from one HEI, but the sentiment is an echo from Forsberg et al.'s (2018) consensus statement on working in RI in research-performing organisations. They outlined thirteen key issues, with the second relating to providing education, training and mentoring for researchers in RI. Forsberg et al. (2018) and Casci and Adams' (2020)

point around training is in line with national and international guidelines in relation to RI and its impact on the research culture (All European Academies, 2017; National Research Integrity Forum, 2019; Science Europe, 2022). A key message from Forsberg et al. (2018) and Casci and Adams (2020) is that professional development is required to enable promotion of a positive research culture.

In the literature, professional learning and professional development are used interchangeably, but for the purposes of the dissertation, it is worth distinguishing between the two. Guskey (2002) and Porritt et al. (2017) explain professional learning as being wide and varied incorporating learning from new technology and attending seminars, to completing a further education qualification and beyond. Earley and Porritt (2009) alternatively outline that professional development is where professional learning is put into practice and becomes embedded in culture that leads to change. Hargreaves (2011) phrases this succinctly in that professional development is where "the object is to improve what teachers do, not merely what they know", (p.10). This links back to Casci and Adams (2020) with learnings on RI needing to be implemented in order to make practical changes. What is evident from the policy and practitioner contexts on RI, is that training is needed to influence change in researchers' behaviour relating to RI, therefore the literature on professional development will be discussed.

Stoll et al. (2012) and Kilpert et al. (2022) posit that if academics wish to develop professionally, doing so collaboratively appears to be the most effective way, with professional learning communities (PLCs), or communities of practice, being appropriate modes of doing this. Collaboration is an integral component to research and as such intertwined with research culture (National Research Integrity Forum, 2022; Science Europe, 2022). Furthermore, the growing emphasis on OR practices in terms of openness of results, data, protocols and others aspects of the research process (European Commission et al., 2020) is also a key component of collaboration (National Open Research Forum, 2019; European Commission, 2019).

Stoll et al.'s (2012) review of the literature on professional learning communities (PLCs), albeit in a school context, found that PLCs' main component for overall effectiveness was sustainable improvement and capacity building, both of which complement the agenda of promoting a positive research culture (Hanover Research, 2014; Science Europe, 2015; Science Europe, 2022). However, it

is also worth noting that not all professional development initiatives are successful. Stoll et al. (2012) also found that in order to be confident that professional development will be a success, a clear purpose needs to be shared and realised. Earley and Porritt (2009) carried out a study measuring effective practices in professional development across 670 schools as well as local authorities and HEIs. One of the findings from Earley and Porritt (2009) was that clarity of purpose needs to be to the fore of professional development along with being sustainable through diverse offerings of professional development, including but not limited to, coaching, conferences, mentoring, peer-assisted learning, seminars. Bubb and Earley (2013), in their mixed methods study involving case studies and surveys across 600 schools in England, found that the training should be discipline specific, as opposed to all encompassing. Feedback shared in Bubb and Earley's (2013) work on the use of training was:

In an attempt to include the whole school workforce, too little attention had been paid to addressing the needs and taking account of the feelings of a range of staff. (p.241.)

Earley and Porritt (2009) also found that in order for professional development and interest in the topic to be sustainable there needs to be evidence of its benefit and overall impact. Based on a school setting, Everard et al. (2004) advocate that evidence should be gathered that professional development works and has impact. While Guskey (2002) states this evidence may be through participant feedback, to monitoring the impact on organisation support and change, to measuring participants' use of new knowledge skills.

In combination with professional development having a clear purpose, being discipline specific and allowing for feedback, Murphy et al. (2006), Kania and Kramer (2011) and Senge et al. (2014) found that for change from professional development to be self-sustaining within a system, it should be underpinned by a culture that promotes reflection and creative conversations. In the context of the dissertation, in the promotion of a positive research culture in HEIs, this realistically cannot be achieved through one person leading and giving instruction and direction (Faraci et al., 2013); instead for the learning to be distributed effectively there should be a culture of learning to enhance skills and support effective learning (Murphy et al., 2006). Murphy et al. (2006) are advocates for learning communities in an educational setting which should "create a culture of collaboration and the systems, operations, and policies that provide the infrastructure for that collegial culture" (p.21). These findings of culture of collaboration address the aforementioned National Research Integrity

Forum (2022) and Science Europe (2022) stance of the link between collaboration and a positive research culture.

Learning communities are to the fore of Kools and Stoll's (2016) work, who discuss the role and impact of PLCs and joint practice development (JPD). They state that the former maps onto professional learning within a system or organisation, while the latter relates to learning from colleagues or organisations external to the system (Fielding et al., 2005). While learning through external engagement has its benefits in overall new learning processes and may potentially create strategic alliances with external systems in JPD, there are clear obstacles in terms of stakeholder time to partake in the professional learning. For example, in their writing about schools Hargreaves and Fullan (2012) note academics often feel "overloaded and pulled in all directions" (p.34). This can also be applied to researchers in HE, where there has been a recently reported crisis in wellbeing due to unmanageable workloads for PhD students with lack of training (Woolston, 2019), postdoctoral scholars with working long hours and little job security (Woolston, 2020) and Ayres' (2022) opinion piece recently calling out the need for a platform to discuss researcher wellbeing openly.

In Earley and Porritt's (2009) study measuring the effective practices in professional development that included HEIs in the sample, they found a key message that underpinned their findings was the importance of being strategic in the leadership of professional development. This aligns with RI, in terms of planning and adapting to demands both internal and external to HEIs and trying to overcome pressure and challenges in the leadership around promoting a positive research culture.

Pressures and Challenges in Research Culture Leadership

Working with stakeholders across disciplines can be a challenge in the management and consensus on what good research practices are, along with awareness of questionable research practices (QRPs) (National Research Integrity Forum, 2022). National Research Integrity Forum (2022) is a framework providing guidance to researchers on how to reinforce a culture of responsible conduct of research (RCR) in their collaborations, along with avoiding incidences of research misconduct and QRPs in these collaborations. The framework developed by Irish HEI research leaders, outline general responsibilities of collaborators in a research study, along with steps to protect good research

practices and dissemination of outputs with contributions acknowledged appropriately. National Research Integrity Forum (2022) state that agreement requires leadership and governance arrangements, along with guidelines in how to handle disputes, however, National Research Integrity Forum (2022) does not go as far as suggesting the types of leadership required to implement the framework.

From Mårtensson et al.'s (2016) review of policy and practitioner context documents relating to research quality, they posit a concept hierarchy of research quality based on four overarching headings on research outputs being credible, contributory, communicable and conforming, that should be useful if carrying out research with collaborators. Similar as National Research Integrity Forum (2022), suggesting the types of leadership required to implement the hierarchy was beyond the scope of the work by Mårtensson et al. (2016). Labib et al. (2022) outlines the learnings from a Science Committee established at Tilburg University in 2012, that explored different forms of governance to foster RI and based on this case study they posit a few recommendations, one being that conversations around governance of good research practices and research quality should occur at the start of a research collaboration and involve the researchers in establishing the RI rules. Involving the researchers in the conversations is analogous to successful collective leadership as posited by Senge et al. (2014). Furthermore Labib et al. (2022) believe an effective approach is to implement the rules gradually to allow sufficient time to embed in the collaborative research culture, along with ensuring regular review and assessment of the rules as the research progresses. A limitation to Labib et al. (2022) is that the findings are based on a case study, which suggests that further research is needed before it can be determined as representative, or at least replicated by other scholars before been seen as definitive. Notwithstanding the sample size, given the under-researched topic of leadership and RI, Labib et al.'s (2022) findings are useful.

The Higher Education Authority (2020) references RI (and RE) as one of their seven elements of good practice in RCR. They also advocate leadership in principles of "honesty, accuracy, objectivity and methodological rigour in the conduct of research" (Higher Education Authority, 2020, p.2) to underpin RI. These principles are analogous to All European Academies' (2017) four core principles of reliability, honesty, respect and accountability in research. A challenge when it comes to promoting a positive research culture underpinned by RI, is that there are times when RI is automatically associated with research misconduct [Nature (Ed.), 2019]. Research misconduct relates to fabrication, falsification

and plagiarism (FFP) of research, along with other QRPs, including but not limited to, withholding results, citing selectively and manipulating authorship (All European Academies, 2017; National Research Integrity Forum, 2019, Robishaw et al., 2019). While RI relates to what is good in research in terms of quality, relevance and overall reliability for wider society to trust in the research outputs (Science Europe, 2015).

In the recent framework for the organisation of research by Science Europe (2022), drafted by a working group on research culture, OR practices, with openness and transparency for all aspects of research, where possible, is seen as a key component of the organisation of research. In order for HEIs to be eligible for European funding they will need to show that they are working towards being in line with these expectations as much as possible (Horizon Europe, 2021). A challenge that HEIs face in terms of meeting the criteria to be eligible for European funding and leadership in OR is to ensure they have the necessary infrastructure to curate and store research outputs in accordance with principles that ensure that outputs are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) (Wilkinson et al., 2016). Haven et al. (2022) collates opinions of practitioners on the relationship between RI and OR, and what is required of the researcher and HEI to implement both in the research culture. One of the main points from Haven et al. (2022) is that in order for researchers to carry out research in as open a manner as possible, then the correct supports need to be in place. In an Irish research context, this is a sentiment also stated in Technological University Research Network (2019):

Digital infrastructure is required for effective research collaborations, particularly internationally. Researchers need to communicate and share resources securely and efficiently. (p.31.)

Wilkinson et al.'s (2016) work on OR intertwines with the findings from Muczyk and Reimann (1987) and Kania and Kramer (2011) in the wider topic of educational leadership where the real challenge for leadership in a system is overcoming the lack of supportive resources and infrastructure to enable the sustainability of change. The findings from a very recent qualitative study on stakeholder experiences of RI support in HEIs, based on researchers across three European countries, by Evans et al. (2022), reinforced the importance of a whole HEI approach when embedding RI and OR in the culture. Evans et al. (2022) found that stakeholders believe it is the HEI's responsibility rather than just the researcher to promote a positive research culture. Evans et al.'s (2022) study does not delve

in leadership models required to react to the paper's findings, but there may be synergies between this dissertation in response to its research questions and outputs from Evans et al.'s (2022).

Ireland's recently published research and innovation strategic plan (Department of Further and Higher Education, Research, Innovation and Science, 2022) aims to position research and innovation at the centre of addressing challenges impacting society, economy and environment. As part of the strategy there is a pillar for research culture which states the aim to "embed consistent good research practices to drive research excellence and quality of outcomes" (p.54). To achieve this, required actions include oversight structures, OR, RI and performance frameworks. Science Europe's (2022) position statement on the organisation of research also state the importance of leadership in RI (and RE), with openness (and transparency) in the overall research culture.

Sustainability of a system has been mentioned many times in this chapter when referencing the work of Murphy et al. (2006), Kania and Kramer (2011), Senge et al. (2014) and Kools and Stoll (2016). In Kania and Kramer's (2011) work – which was based on a study of more than 300 leaders of local organisations including presidents of eight universities and community colleges – one of their findings was that in order for change to be sustained there needs to be push back on the funders. They argue there needs to be:

...a fundamental change in how funders see their role, from funding organizations to leading a long-term process of social change. It is no longer enough to fund an innovative solution created by a single nonprofit or to build that organization's capacity. Instead, funders must help create and sustain the collective processes, measurement reporting systems, and community leadership that enable cross-sector coalitions to arise and thrive. (p.41.)

In European Commission et al.'s (2020) scoping report on reproducibility of research results, the responsibility of the funder is highlighted in recognising good research practices [analogous to Kania and Kramer (2011)], in that:

Funders need to fund and incentivise reproducibility to assist the efforts of results producers for the benefit of users...by ensuring that there are incentives for re-use of the results, rather than continuous re-doing; by supporting basic infrastructures for the preservation and sharing of underlying data and method, among other actions. (p.16.)

In the context of the dissertation, pushback on funding agencies occurs in terms of researcher assessment. Researchers that work in the areas of RI and OR are not always recognised by the funding agencies (Wellcome Trust, 2020). While often the culture of “publish or perish” remains a staple where the more you publish the better, to the potential detriment of value and substance (Neill, 2008; Rawat and Meena, 2014). The current methods of research assessment put pressure on researchers to target performance metrics as opposed to impact on society and the wider community (Curry et al., 2020). Curry et al.’s (2020) working paper led by senior global research leaders outline emerging forms of research assessment, including but not limited to, the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment, DORA (Declaration on Research Assessment, 2012), the Leiden manifesto (Hicks, 2015) and the Hong Kong Principles, HKP (Moher et al. 2020). These forms of research assessment with a focus on qualitative assessment - e.g., a narrative curriculum vitae (CV) - of research outputs as opposed to quantitative are a shift away from “publish or perish” as written about by Neill (2008) and Rawat and Meena (2014) from their viewpoints as an editor of a journal and researchers, respectively. The need for funders to recognise and ensure implementation of new research assessment forms is the next step. Horbach et al. (2022) posit a consensus view that funders develop and implement a Research Integrity Promotion Plan (RIPP) in order to:

...support, safeguard, and incentivise, or even mandate, responsible research practices from research organizations and researchers. (p.3.)

Recommendations of RIPP is an output from Standard Operating Procedures for Research Integrity (SOPs4RI) consortium, which is multi-partner project funded by the European Commission. SOPs4RI consortium have identified six topics for funders to adopt ranging from compliance with RI standards to selection of grant applications to dealing with internal breaches of RI (Standard Operating Procedures for Research Integrity, 2019).

In recent months, Science Europe et al. (2022), building on their intention to do so in Science Europe (2021), have published a vision for reforming research assessment with a movement towards recognising diversity of contributions to research, assessment of research based on qualitative evaluation as opposed to metrics and other quantitative indicators, abandonment of inappropriate uses of the journal impact factor and the use of rankings for research organisations. While, this

movement will be slow with signatories to the framework commencing in September 2022, there appears to be hope that the recent agreement is a step forward given that over 350 organisations have worked collectively on the agreement over the past four years, and it has the support of the European Commission [Nature (Ed.), 2022].

In August 2022, a memo signed by President Biden demanded all federally funded research in the USA become openly available without restrictions or embargo (Office of Science and Technology Policy, 2022). This included both resulting publications and generated data. While the primary focus for the dissertation is the European research landscape, the recent demand from President Biden shows that some countries are ahead of Europe and in the case of the USA, federal agencies are required to have a RIPP as proposed by Horbach et al. (2022) in the European context.

Federal agencies should take actions to ensure that these elements of scientific and research integrity are in place in order to strengthen public trust in federally funded science. (Office of Science and Technology Policy, 2022, pp.5-6.)

While in Europe, Horbach et al.'s (2022) work is a recommendation, in the USA the Office of Science and Technology Policy's (2022) work is a mandate for change to promote a positive research culture.

A recent report by Chairelli et al. (2022) on behalf of UK Research and Innovation, Cancer Research UK and GuildHE on facets of RI. Chairelli et al.'s (2022) study involved a desk review of over 120 sources, along with a set of 22 stakeholder interviews with individuals from Europe, North America and the UK. They found the importance of establishing norms along with ranking indicators of RI in terms of what should have a high feasibility for immediate progress (e.g., accountability when researchers and HEIs carry out research misconduct; transparent and responsible sharing of research outputs), while marked as low or medium feasibility to be considered but in consultation with appropriate stakeholders (e.g., following norms, standards and protocols; care and respect to the integrity of the research record).

What is evident from the pressure and challenges in research culture leadership, is that change is required to overcome these (Casci and Adams, 2020; Curry et al., 2020; Mejlgaard et al., 2020).

There are many change management theories within literature, with the works of Lewin (1947), Kotter (1996) and Fullan (2007) being particularly prevalent. Irrespective of a HEI trying to promote a positive research culture, or exploring other academic concerns, for example student retention, infrastructure or scholarship, what is clear from the literature is the HEI landscape is constantly changing and appears to be moving at a faster pace than ever before (Singh, 2001; Mowles et al., 2018; World Economic Forum, 2019).

Lewin (1947) places importance on human change when migrating through three steps of initially highlighting that change is needed, to then implementing the change and, finally embedding a new model in the culture. Lewin (1947) highlights the importance of regular communication throughout the change process as being key. Although there are instances in the literature of Lewin's (1947) three step process being too simple and not appreciating the complexity of human behaviour, it is clear that many posit that the model lays the foundation underlying any change (Cummings, 2015; Burnes, 2020). Kotter's (1996) change model provides eight steps to positive change management, which range from creating a sense of urgency that change is needed to forming and sharing a vision to embedding change. Although Kotter's (1996) work is primarily focussed on the business and entrepreneurial world, given the ever-changing landscape in the HE sectors (Singh, 2001; Mowles et al., 2018; World Economic Forum, 2019), the learnings from Kotter (1996) are strong. Fullan (2007), based on original work from 1982, uses a three-step model with a focus on the period leading to change – initiation - to gauging experiences of the change process – implementation - to embedding or discarding the change – incorporation.

In terms of leadership and RI, and promoting a positive research culture, there appears to be a strong synergy with Kotter's (1996) initial steps. Kotter's (1996, p.23) step to creating a sense of urgency is analogous to points by Kania and Kramer (2011) and Science Europe et al. (2022) in terms of communication; Building a coalition is comparable to fostering commitment and engagement across boundaries (Senge et al., 2014; Casci and Adams, 2020); Form a vision for buy-in from management could be mapped to the work of Prysor and Henley (2018) and Mejlgaard et al. (2020); Enlist an army should correspond to forming PLCs and JPDs (Stoll et al., 2012; Kools and Stoll, 2016; Kilpert et al., 2022).

A clear synergy existing between Lewin (1947), Kotter (1996) and Fullan (2007) is communication pre-, during- and post-change, however, Kotter (1996) for reasons outlined above appears to be more applicable in the context of promoting a positive research culture in a HEI. Furthermore, a common error mentioned by Kotter (1996) in leading change is neglecting to anchor changes firmly in the culture which is underpinned by trust. Here Kotter's (1996) steps speaks to Casci and Adams' (2020) work on the need for implementation and practical change, along with the outputs from Science Europe (2015) and Wellcome Trust (2020) in how RI is the basis for researchers to trust each other as well as the research record.

Summary

This literature review has covered leadership practices spanning directive to collective mapping to a research culture setting, while being cognisant of the current research policy and practitioner contexts (All European Academies, 2017; National Research Integrity Forum, 2019; Science Europe, 2022). With the ever-changing research landscape (Singh, 2001; Mowles et al., 2018), literature across leadership theory that promotes and encourages adaption and learning (Heifetz et al., 2004; Stoll et al., 2012; Kools and Stoll, 2016) within a system was discussed. Throughout the review challenges impacting promoting a positive research culture, including time for researchers to professionally develop, the need for appropriate infrastructures and resources, under the ever changing HE landscape in terms of internal and external agency demands are also discussed.

The review of the literature has aided the development of the following research questions:

- Primary research question: What type of leadership models do senior research leaders find most effective in promoting a positive research culture in HEIs?
- Secondary research question: What practices have senior research leaders found most effective in leading change and promoting a positive research culture in their HEI, in line with changing internal and external requirements?

In parallel with the research questions, the following hypotheses will be tested:

1. Senior research leaders need to adapt their leadership style to respond to the regular changing of compliance and enhancement issues in HE research integrity.

2. Collective leadership is an appropriate approach to lead change to embed good research practices in the research culture.
3. In order to overcome leadership obstacles to promoting good research practices, the wider research community should be involved in policy and procedure development.

The following chapters will use primary research to explore the above-mentioned research questions and hypotheses, with the aim of contributing to establishing evidence informed recommendations on leadership practices of RI to promote a positive research culture in HEIs, supported by existing literature.

3. Methodology

There are many definitions for research, with Quality and Qualifications Ireland (2020) stating:

Research is a process to discover new knowledge, through systematic investigation. Through research, hypotheses are investigated, facts are established, or new interpretations of data or texts suggested. It is a process of gathering and analysing information, designed to develop or contribute to knowledge, increase or revise knowledge. (p.11.)

Essentially research is more than gathering data, but it is about discovering new knowledge validly and methodically, underpinned by an appropriate methodology (Goddard and Melville, 2001), with appreciation for research paradigms (Hanan, 2006), study types (Goswami, 2011), research instruments (Wilkinson and Birmingham, 2003), methods and timeframes (Connolly, 2016), along with data collection and analyses (Palinkas et al., 2015; Male, 2016). In parallel with aforementioned attributes of a research methodology there needs to be awareness of ethical considerations (British Educational Research Association, 2018) including data storage and retention (University College London, 2011 and 2020) and researcher positionality (Holmes and Gary, 2020).

In this chapter an overview of attributes to research methodologies are outlined with a rationale for selecting the final methodology for the dissertation. At various points through selecting various attributes of the methodology, awareness of the limitations to these choices are discussed.

Research Paradigms and Study Type

Research paradigms, or philosophical frameworks, can vary from positivism to interpretivism or scientific to phenomenological (Thomas, 2017). Positivism, or scientific, is often mapped to research findings that are objective with support and verification by experiments, mathematical proofs and other quantitative methods. Interpretivism, or phenomenological, are regularly mapped to research findings from qualitative studies involving subjective perceptions of participants (Palaiologou et al., 2016). The paradigm of choice is often led by the research hypothesis, current state of knowledge in the literature and how data is to be collected (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017). If the aim of the research is to gather data from human participants and to be objective, explain relationships and/or differences without concern for rapport with participants involved or potential understanding of

why certain data is collected, then scientific may be an appropriate paradigm (Hanan, 2006). Conversely, a phenomenological paradigm allows for the opportunity to build a rapport with participants and thus potentially validate why certain data is collected, but with the limitation that the data collected may not be representative of the population and may not be generalisable (Thomas, 2017).

Qualitative data usually provides rich, deep insights, and while the data may not be generalisable or representative can function as a starting point when exploring an under-researched topic (Palaiologou et al., 2016). With the potential insights gained from qualitative data combined with the lack of existing research in the field of leadership in RI, it was deemed appropriate to use the phenomenological paradigm. The benefit of being able to discuss leadership with participants, with the opportunity to have follow-up questions depending on the data collected, outweighed the potential limitations of research findings.

The purpose of this research is to observe potential patterns to support developing hypotheses, as opposed to testing an existing theory. This is analogous to inductive as opposed to deductive reasoning, mapping to exploratory as opposed to confirmatory analyses (Goswami, 2011). With no set leadership model defined for RI, it followed for this research study to be exploratory and inductive in the first instance. As is traditional for such exploratory studies, findings are presented descriptively as opposed to inferentially (Goswami, 2011; O'Shea, 2013).

Research Instrument, Method and Timeframe

Research Instrument

When carrying out qualitative data analysis, Hox and Boeije (2005) argue that there are benefits to both primary and secondary data to shape findings. In this case however, as discussed in previous chapters, there is little evidence or discussion on successful leadership models in RI, and as such there is no secondary data available that could be used to explore the hypotheses. Furthermore, with the aim of the study being to observe potential patterns to support developing hypotheses under the phenomenological paradigm, qualitative data collection methods using primary data was deemed appropriate (Connolly, 2016).

There are many research instruments that align with qualitative methods from surveys with open ended questions, to focus groups, to interviews, to mixed methods (Wilkinson and Birmingham, 2003). Potentially for a broader study on the synthesis between leadership and RI, a mixed methods approach would be advantageous. For example, a survey designed to gauge senior research leaders' perception of RI in the research culture, combined with focus groups and content analysis on HEI policy and procedures on RI could result in findings that would be generalisable, representative, and thus lying within an overall scientific paradigm. However, with the aim of this study being to develop a hypothesis through dialogue with participants with the opportunity to ask follow-up questions, interviews were deemed appropriate. To ensure that certain questions were covered within the interview timeframe, but with flexibility to build a rapport and ask follow-up questions to potentially interesting responses, semi-structured interviews were used over structured or open interviews (Adams, 2015).

While it is beneficial to collect primary data, which is often more relevant to a research study than secondary data, Connolly (2016) found that with primary data the scale of the data being collected is often limited by time and access constraints. Notwithstanding the limitation around sample size and timeframe of the overall research study, given the little research available to date on leadership and RI, primary data collection was deemed to be appropriate, with semi-structured interviews used for data collection.

Method and Timeframe

The semi-structured interviews were framed around four overarching themes:

1. Compliance and enhancement issues in Higher Education research,
2. Leadership obstacles to promoting good research practices,
3. Procedures around research misconduct,
4. Leading change to embed good research practices in the research culture.

These themes and supporting questions were derived from current research policy and practitioner contexts both nationally and internationally (All European Academies, 2017; European Commission, 2019; National Research Integrity Forum, 2019), and based on literature discussed in the previous chapter. The flow and order of questions asked in the interviews varied between interviews, based

on learnings from previous interviews, and as such formed an iterative approach as described by Male (2016).

With the power of hindsight, based on the number of questions used per theme, as outlined in Appendix i, and the time available to carry out the interview, if this research were to be repeated, reducing the themes to three would be worth considering. This would have given the opportunity to gain deeper insights on a more focussed area. Based on Male's (2016) iterative approach to carrying out interviews, themes 1, 2 and 4 were where most time was spent in the interviews, with little time remaining to focus on theme 3.

Sampling Method

In 2008, the European Network of Research Integrity Offices (ENRIO) was founded as a European Network to enhance RI within Europe with an emphasis on growing international cooperation. ENRIO has many aims, one of which is to support and advise countries that lack a national structure relating to policies, procedures and training in RI (European Network of Research Integrity Offices, 2008). Based on ENRIO's aim, the organisation seemed a logical first step in determining a sample for this exploratory study. Nine countries were founding members of ENRIO, including Finland, the Netherlands and the United Kingdom (UK). Based on having contacts from the researcher's own professional network in these three countries, they were prioritised. Through this opportunistic and purposive sampling approach, the aim of this study was to contact senior research leaders in HEIs in these countries and examine their leadership practices in relation to implementing RI policies and procedures, to establish effective approaches to promoting a positive research culture in their respective HEI.

In order to determine which HEIs per country should potentially be included in the research study, membership of the European Association of Research Management and Administration (EARMA) was utilised. EARMA, founded in 1995, represents the community of Research Managers and Administrators within Europe. EARMA members' main remit is to build the European research area that forms the link between research funding organisations and the wider community, along with bridging the legal and cultural differences between countries, and between industry and academia (European Association of Research Management and Administration, 1995).

Working from an EARMA database, with Finland, the Netherlands and the UK, as founding members of ENRIO, there are 13, 18 and 6 HEIs that are members of EARMA, respectively. Initially, this yielded too small a research population (37 HEIs). It was recently reported in *Nature* (2021) that in its first year of existence, the Swedish research misconduct agency was inundated with alleged cases of research misconduct (Else, 2021). With the potential learning from leadership practices of RI and that the researcher's professional network included researchers from Swedish HEIs, Sweden was also included in the population. With Sweden included (ENRIO member since 2009), this expanded the population by an additional 13 Swedish HEIs that are also members of EARMA.

EARMA members from Finland, Sweden, the Netherlands and the UK yielded a research population of 50 HEIs. Applying the Malterud et al. (2016) model of requiring a sample size in qualitative studies to be guided by the aim of the study, sample specificity, use of established theory, quality of dialogue, and analysis strategy, the interview schedule included a 10% sample (5 HEIs).

In parallel with potential researcher bias, which is negated by the sample selection process as outlined above, there is the potential for respondent bias with selecting a sample from EARMA membership only, where the sample chosen may contain participants with similar mindsets and background, analogous to potential "groupthink" as outlined by Janis (1972). However, it is felt for an exploratory study with the aim of arriving at general conclusions, as opposed to testing a hypothesis, that using the EARMA database as a mechanism to create a shortlist for potential participants across a variety of HEIs to be included in the study was sufficient. Another mechanism for selecting HEIs could have been some form of ranking system or University league tables – e.g. the *Times Higher Education World University Rankings*, the *QS World Rankings* or the *Academic Ranking of World Universities* - but given the negative press relating to rankings, leagues tables and misusing some quantitative metrics (Barnett and Gadd, 2022; Neylon, 2022), it was felt that for a study involving integrity and good practice, selecting a sample from a form of ranking table would not be appropriate. This is especially pertinent considering that:

From a statistical perspective there are some serious problems with the [league] tables which lead to reductionism, gaming, and ultimately poor decision-making. (Barnett and Gadd, 2022, p.2.)

With the small sample size combined with the phenomenological paradigm, there was the risk of not uncovering generalisable findings (Hanan, 2006), however, given the exploratory nature of the research study and the paradigm of choice, there was the expectation to still obtain information-rich data (Patton, 1990) to aid in the development of leadership in RI training and strategy in future.

To obtain the sample, the researcher contacted senior research leaders from five HEIs, isolated based on the researcher's own professional network, thus leading to opportunistic sampling. Brady (2006) states in the context of opportunistic sampling that the sampling method should tally with the epistemology of the paradigm. Goertz and Mahoney (2012) posit the differences between epistemology and ontology philosophies, with the latter relating to concepts that already exist and the former relating to the manner and conditions for what exists, analogous to the study of knowledge. For the purposes of this research study with the aim of understanding good practice in leadership for RI, an opportunistic sampling method combined with purposive sampling was deemed appropriate under the epistemology branch of philosophy.

With purposive sampling, also known as judgement sampling, being a non-probability sampling method, whereby not everyone from the population has an equal opportunity to be included in the research study, there is a risk of having research findings with bias (Palinkas et al., 2015). In this instance, there is the potential to have researcher bias, in that the researcher made a judgement as to who should be included in the study or not. Palinkas et al. (2015) states that researcher bias is only a major disadvantage when such judgements are ill-conceived or poorly considered. For this dissertation, the sample selection from ENRIO to EARMA had been well-considered with the logic for participants inclusion being clearly thought out, as outlined above, and feasible given the time constraints of the dissertation.

Ethical Considerations

As a core principle, educational research should do no harm and ideally benefit participants, researchers and the wider community, and should be carried out with integrity and honesty to participants throughout the research process (British Educational Research Association, 2018). Ethical issues raised with human participants include informed consent, respect for autonomy and confidentiality (British Educational Research Association, 2018). Furthermore, the research process

needs to be rigorous and impartial and executed to the highest possible standards so that it can contribute to the wider community and hence that the input from participants is not devalued. Participants' right to withdraw, along with the right to be debriefed at study end should always be ensured also. These are the principles to which the current research study was framed and carried out, with a copy of the UCL ethics approval letter included in Appendix ii.

Informed Consent

Participants were contacted over email and provided full details of the research study prior to being invited to the interview, so they had the opportunity to ask questions and the right to not participate. Along with an outline of the topics to be discussed in the interview, the email included a consent form, along with an open invitation to contact the researcher if additional information was required. Appendices iii and iv include the Information Leaflet and Consent Form, respectively, that were shared with participants in the original email. To avoid potential oversubscription, there was a one-week wait for a response to the invitation to participate in the research study, at which point if there was no response after one week (with a gentle reminder email after three days), an email was sent to another potential participant. Potential participants were made aware that it was entirely their choice whether to participate or not in the research study and that not being involved had no negative impact on them at any time. In order to proceed to the interview stage, participants were required to return a signed copy of the Consent Form. Consent was also asked verbally at the start of the interview (see Appendix i).

Safeguarding Participants and Right to Withdraw

All participants were over the age of 18 years, not part of a vulnerable group and had the appropriate capacity to decide to consent to participating in the research study as outlined by British Educational Research Association (2018). The interviews had broad themes, that were shared with participants in advance of the interview, so there was a narrow scope for participants to experience anxiety, discomfort and/or embarrassment during the study. Nonetheless, participants were advised that they had the right to not respond to a question and move onto the next question or stop the interview at any time should they have felt uncomfortable or not wish to answer.

Confidentiality and Data Management

Clear and accurate records of the research procedures followed and of the results obtained have been maintained throughout the lifecycle of the research study in line with national and international requirements (University College London, 2011; All European Academies, 2017; National Research Integrity Forum, 2019; University College London, 2020).

Given the small purposive and opportunistic sampling approach, participants' names were not recorded and instead interview participants were referred to as Participant 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5. Hence, data gathered was anonymous. Furthermore, in general, the reporting of the data was not concerned with individual responses as responses were aggregated to deliver information organised by emerging themes. Where it was necessary to include quotes from individuals to support findings, quotes were anonymised, and not mapped to participant number, to ensure that the rights of that participant are respected and that the participant remains anonymous as best as possible, with any specific identifying characteristics and personal data redacted.

All data is held on the researcher's UCL OneDrive repository. Contained within the repository is a folder for Interviews, in which each sub-folder contains all documents pertaining to a single interview - recording of interviews (until destroyed) and transcripts (both the raw version and secondary identifiers removed version). The proof of informed consent was stored in a separate folder on OneDrive. A research data management plan (DMP) has been created using DMP Online (Digital Curation Centre, 2005) to which the supervisor of this research study has access to. A copy of the DMP, as on 12 September 2022, is included in Appendix v. Data will be stored for one year after the completion of the dissertation and overall grade awarded to allow the possibility of dissemination at a conference and/or in peer-reviewed open access publication. After this point the data obtained will be destroyed in line with UCL's Records Retention Schedule for files relating to research data (University College London, 2020).

Finally, upon completion of the grading of the dissertation, the dissertation will be preserved open access, for dissemination with the wider research community in UCL's institutional repository, (University College London Discovery, 2022).

Researcher Positionality

As a researcher, facilitator of training and advocate of RI, ethics and OR there are justifiable concerns around a potential power-play in relation to expected answers in the semi-structured interviews based on the researcher's own potential ontological and epistemological beliefs (Holmes and Gary, 2020). Holmes and Gary (2020) explicitly focus on postgraduate researchers which is poignant given the dissertation is part fulfilment of an MBA. Reflexivity in tandem with positionality is advocated by Holmes and Gary (2020), along with Corlett and Mavin (2018), where they highlight the importance of a researcher being aware that their positionality may change over time and a researcher should reflect on this positionality and realise that if it is not fixed, then they should be open to other opinions and positions. Of course, positionality is important in research as well, as it motivates the researcher's inherent understanding and interest in the research topic (Bourke, 2014; Coghlan and Brydon-Miller, 2014), but should not lead, influence or bias any aspect of the research design and overall conduct of research.

Potential biases and criticality of the various attributes to the research methodology have been covered in the previous subsections with the exception of the operational aspect of carrying out the semi-structured interviews and what follows. With the research study focusing on RI and its position in terms of good practice and overall research culture, in order to mitigate potential researcher positionality, as posited by Thomas (2017), the first question to participants, after the control questions, was a general question on "What do you consider to be good research practice?". The response to this question guided and shaped the remainder of the interview, as opposed to the researcher's potential insider positionality (Thomas, 2017).

Following the interview, another approach adopted to mitigate against potential researcher positionality, and potential misinterpretation of responses was to share the final version of interview transcripts with participants. Sharing the final transcripts with participants was a method of data verification around the transcript being a fair and accurate representation of the interview and participants' intention (Male, 2016).

With ethical considerations to the forefront in the implications of the chosen the research method, next step was around the data collection.

Data Collection

At the time of data collection, there were 13, 18, 13 and 6 HEIs from Finland, the Netherlands, the UK and Sweden respectively, that were members of EARMA. From this population, the plan was to sample 1, 2, 1 and 1 senior research leaders respectively, from each HEI using a combination of opportunistic and purposive sampling. Interviews were carried out online using MS Teams or Zoom, depending on the virtual meeting platform that suited participants, and ranged in duration from 50 to 55 minutes. Interviews took place over a six-week period, from May to June 2022. The initial plan was to carry out one interview per week, allowing time for using an iterative approach (Male, 2016) in between interviews, however, there was a delay in the final interview due to lack of availability of potential participants from HEIs in Finland.

After three attempts to contact different senior research leaders from HEIs in Finland, allowing one week for a potential participant to reply, the researcher had to select a different country as all alternative options to recruit given time constraints for the research study were exhausted. At this point, the researcher was reminded of a potential participant from the UK that was recommended to contact in another interview, if time allowed. Although, a participant from the UK was already interviewed at this stage, the proposed participant was from a different jurisdiction and had a different research background from the first participant from the UK, which was deemed appropriate to gain further insight into international leaderships practices in RI. The researcher contacted the senior research leader without mentioning the referral from another study participant, in order to maintain a consistency with how all participants were approached. Thankfully the senior research leader from the UK agreed to participate in the study.

All participants consented beforehand to have the interviews recorded. Following recording of the interviews, transcription was carried out with all secondary identifiers (any specific identifying characteristics and personal data) of participants removed. As previously mentioned, the final transcripts were shared with participants and verified as being a fair and accurate representation of the interview.

Data Analysis

After approval from participants on the transcript content, transcripts were imported into NVivo (Release 1.6.1) for data analysis. NVivo is a qualitative data analysis computer software package produced by QSR International Pty Ltd that helps qualitative researchers to organise, analyse and find insights in unstructured or qualitative data such as interviews, open-ended survey responses, journal articles, social media and web content (QSR International Pty Ltd, 2020). Initially, there was a three-fold approach to the data analysis for this dissertation involving a priori codes (Male, 2016), emergent codes (Braun and Clarke, 2006) and word frequency analysis (Feng and Behar-Horenstein, 2019).

The mapping of extracted text to codes aligned with the phenomenological paradigm, with an interpretative approach used dependent on the researcher's subjective opinion that was informed by the literature review. The transcription of interviews combined with the multiple reviewing of the subsequent transcripts in creation of codes enabled the researcher to be immersed in the data. In parallel with developing codes, memos and annotations were recorded when potential segments of text relating to a participant's opinion was consistent with other participants and/or informative for future use. Furthermore, the memos were a useful mechanism for shortlisting quotes that would be used to support the discussion in the dissertation.

A priori codes

Coding is an interpretive technique, aligning with the phenomenological paradigm, that both organises data into themes and provides a mechanism to introduce interpretations of the data (Sang and Sitko, 2015; Male, 2016). Five codes were identified prior to data collection: "Culture change"; "External agencies"; "Good research practice"; "Research misconduct" and "Shared learning environment".

A code may vary from a short sentence, or even word, to multiple paragraphs that suggests how the associated data segments inform the research objectives (Lester et al., 2020). The number of references (text extracts) per code was tallied by NVivo and presented descriptively, using frequency tables and charts, in the dissertation. Charts used in the dissertation were created using the *ggplot2*

package (Wickham, 2016) from the open source statistical programming language, R (R Core Team, 2022). A copy of the script used to generate the charts is included in Appendix vi.

A criticism of the coding method to qualitative data is that it drains the data of its variety, richness and individual character, while Brown et al. (1990, p.136) suggest "the existence of multiple synonyms would lead to partial retrieval of information". Although, Brown et al.'s (1990) posit is fair, and may be the case in other research contexts, in the context of this exploratory research study the codes created, as presented in the upcoming chapters, link these codes, and subsequent themes, soundly to the underlying data and as such are an ideal initial step that should contribute to establishing evidence informed recommendations on leadership practices of RI to promote a positive research culture in HEIs.

Emergent codes

Typically, a priori codes are not exhaustive of all codes in data gathered, with further codes usually emerging from the data analysis. These data-driven codes are founded through open coding, a form of grounded theory based on the literature review (Sang and Sitko, 2015; Male, 2016). These codes emerge upon immersion in the data through multiple reviews of the data obtained from participant responses in the semi-structured interviews.

Word Frequency Analysis

To ensure nothing is missed with the previous mentioned methods to developing codes, a word frequency analysis was applied to explore for any additional codes that were not isolated. Carley (1993) showed the approach of word frequency analysis as beneficial due to important and significant words being used more frequently in open-ended question responses. Also, Jackson and Trochim (2002) stated that word count has its advantages in identifying patterns more easily, verifying a hypothesis and maintaining analytic integrity.

Feng and Behar-Horenstein (2019) outlined a successful process to analyse open-ended responses to questions which was underpinned by word frequency analysis. Using the Feng and Behar-Horenstein (2019) process, words included in the analysis had five or more letters (for example,

words like “we”, “the” and “is” are excluded). Four steps to Feng and Behar-Horenstein’s (2019) analysis applied to the study data were as follows:

1. The open-ended responses to all questions were run through the word frequency analysis function in NVivo using words with stemmed variants (e.g., “research, researches, researcher, researchers” are counted as “research”) with their weighted percentages calculated.
2. Feng and Behar-Horenstein (2019) recommend the most frequently occurring words, with a weighted percentage of at least 0.5%, to serve as potential coded words or references.
3. The word frequency analysis findings are presented as frequency tables and word clouds.
4. The most frequently occurring words (including the stemmed variants) could be coded as response content, also called references, if appropriate.

Word frequency analysis does not come without challenges. When reviewing a reference, a user could find that a frequently occurring word does not contribute to the responses of the questions (Sarica and Luo, 2021). For example, when a participant is asked “What do you consider to be good research practice?” the most frequent word to appear in a response is “research”. However, this word does not overly contribute to the response of the question. In this case, a user would expect a stemmed variant of the word “research” to be mentioned in response to a question about research, but “research” would not be the most accurate code or theme to extract from the question. If a word does not contribute to the response to a question, it can be labelled a “stop-word” from the word frequency analysis, with the word frequency analysis step repeated and subsequent text coding updated. The stop-word of “research” does not mean that any response with the word research is excluded, but more that the word “research” would not appear in the word frequency analysis, therefore improving visualisations of the text data (MAXQDA, 2021).

One stop-words was used for the word frequency analysis. “Research” for reasons as outlined above was treated as a stop-word in the final word frequency analysis outputs.

Finally, in terms of developing codes, it is worth stating that codes developed were based on the surface interpretation of the data, which are called semantic codes. Braun and Clarke (2006) state that the opposite to the development of semantics codes would be latent coding which are derived

from underlying meaning, ideas and assumptions. Given the little research carried out on the topic of leadership and RI, the researcher felt that the most appropriate initial step would be adopting semantic coding as opposed to latent. Latent coding is an alternative approach that could be considered for future research.

From Codes to Themes

Following developing codes, the next step was to group codes that are related to each other under overarching themes. The grouping of related codes is often underpinned by the grounded theory of the research topic and is a form axial coding which is based on a theoretical approach and the deductive thinking of the researcher (Sang and Sitko, 2015). With this method to developing themes, Corbin and Strauss (1990) and Braun and Clarke (2006) label the outputs as theoretical themes as opposed to data-driven themes.

The motivation for developing themes is that:

A theme captures something important about the data in relation to the research question, and represents some level of patterned response or meaning within the data set. (Braun and Clarke, 2006, p.10.)

When collating codes into themes, overarching themes to the entire dataset are applied. Braun and Clarke (2006) advocate that when carrying out analysis on an under-researched topic, such as this research study, that overarching thematic descriptions of the entire dataset, as opposed to nuanced descriptions are more appropriate. The downside of this overarching thematic description may be that some depth and complexity of the data may be lost. Nonetheless given the scale of this study and its novel nature, overarching themes were developed, with these themes summarised using a thematic table (Braun and Clarke, 2006).

The codes were collated based on the principles of grounded theory and review of the references associated with each code. When collating codes there was a need for a consistent and coherent pattern with the references used (Patton, 1990). Patton (1990) states that if the themes do not have an internal homogeneity, in parallel with an external heterogeneity, then the themes are not really

themes. The final overarching themes should have enough data within them, but with the data not being too diverse, in order for them to be reliable (Patton, 1990).

It was expected that in the collation of codes into overarching themes, some codes might not collate overly well, which often can be grouped together to form a miscellaneous theme (Braun and Clarke, 2006). Although, it was expected to develop a miscellaneous theme through the data analysis, this did not turn out to be the case, with all themes developed mapping and addressing aspects of the study's research questions and hypotheses.

Adopting the back and forward analysis described by Braun and Clarke (2006) lead to the final version of themes developed in the dissertation. Braun and Clarke (2006) found that the back and forward movement between data, codes, references and narrative around the developing themes, ensures the final version of themes are an accurate reflection of the data provided by the participants.

Evaluations of the Methodology

With the limited existing research in the area of educational leadership and RI, the researcher felt that use of the phenomenological paradigm to be important. Limitations to the paradigm and complementing attributes of the chosen research methodology are outlined throughout the chapter. Based on the overview of the various attributes and limitation of the outlined research methodology, coupled with the time constraints to carrying out the research study, the decision to carry-out a small-scale exploratory study was deemed appropriate. Semi-structured interviews were used as the research instrument to collect primary data. As a result of these choices, the sampling method, ethical considerations, along with data collection and data analysis plan followed.

The resulting qualitative data from the study interviews, as presented and discussed in later chapters, should be mechanism to obtain original reliable insights into senior research leaders' perceptions of educational leadership to inform the promotion of a positive research culture in HEIs. Given the small sample size of the study, there was the risk of obtaining results that were not going to be generalisable and representative of the population, however, Connolly (2016) and Thomas

(2017) found that small-scale exploratory studies can be useful for providing initial information that could be used to inform a future broader study.

With Finland having numerous examples of promoting good research practice as outlined by Räsänen and Moore (2016) and the Finnish Advisory Board on Research Integrity (2021), there is a missed opportunity in the findings to not have a senior research leader from a HEI in Finland contributing. If expanding this research study in the future, then including a HEI from Finland would be a priority. Notwithstanding a representative from a Finnish HEI not being part of the study, the final distribution of senior research leader participants from the Netherland (2), the UK (2) and Sweden (1) was deemed wide and sufficiently varied that the findings from the interviews should be informative.

The virtual nature to carrying out the interviews was a definite advantage to the data collection method. With virtual interviews, there was greater access to international senior research leaders, along with the capability of recording the interview, hence enabling accurate transcription and notes on physical reactions where applicable. While Jones and Abdelfattah (2020) find that participants sometimes are not ideally prepared for virtual interviews, this researcher found the virtual interview efficient and cannot see how the research study could be actioned to its potential without the virtual nature of the data collection. Furthermore, based on the feedback of data verification of transcripts from participants, they felt their perceptions and intentions were represented fully.

Furthermore, the semi-structured interviews enabled opportunities for follow-up questions to interesting points made by participants. If the study was larger, the possibility for using semi-structured interviews as the research instrument would not have been feasible given the time constraints with the research study, however with the small scale this was successful. With the resulting small sample size, the researcher had to be strategic in sample selection using contacts in HEIs through a combination of opportunistic sampling and purposive sampling. Utilising contacts within HEIs enabled a relatively efficient turnaround in data acquisition. However had this project taken place over a longer period it could have been beneficial to include senior research leaders from other European countries to enhance comparability across jurisdictions. With the recent

declaration in France that they will require PhD students to take a research ethics oath as part of the research studies (Rabesandratana, 2022), it is possible that an interview with a French senior research leader may have been beneficial in learning about leadership practices in their area. This is something that would be incorporated into a future study were this work to be expanded.

A final consideration would have been to include senior research leaders from HEIs in the United States of America (USA). There is the potential for further insightful conversations with senior research leaders from HEIs in the USA based on the recent government led publications demanding for more rigour and transparency in research (United States Government Accountability Office, 2022) and requiring that all federally funded research studies must share their research findings openly and with no cost (Office of Science and Technology Policy, 2022). Furthermore, inclusion of participants from HEIs in the USA would potentially enable a synergy with the recently published results by Chairelli et al.'s (2022) on interviews with individuals from Europe, North America and the UK on facets of RI. While this would have broadened the scope of this project possibly too widely for the limitations of an MBA dissertation, this would be an interesting area to explore in a future project to understand the connections and disparities between approaches in Europe and North America.

Summary

This chapter outlines the approach taken in a small-scale exploratory study of senior research leaders in HEIs across Europe. Notwithstanding the limitations to the research methodology chosen, the overall approach and subsequent data collected and analysed was successful. If the study was to be repeated, with potentially more time available, then expanding the population to include HEIs in other European countries, the USA and other areas globally would provide further insight into global leadership practices to promote a positive research culture in HEIs. However, for this small-scale exploratory study the findings from the data obtained, as presented and discussed in the following chapters, links to the studies research questions. The findings should contribute to establishing evidence informed recommendations on leadership practices of RI to promote a positive research culture in HEIs, that may form initial steps to support institutes' development of leadership in RI training and strategy in future.

4. Overview of Findings

Findings from the data analysis plan, as outlined in the Methodology chapter, are presented in this chapter. Information on participant attributes, along with overall participant contributions to the codes and themes developed are presented. Commentary on how the overarching themes developed address the research questions and hypotheses is also presented.

Participant Attributes

Participants were spread across three countries in Europe, and were either directors (or equivalent) or programme leaders (or equivalent) in RI, with some participants being research active at the time of the study. Participants had been working in the area of promoting RI from three to ten years. Distribution of participant demographics is included in Table 4.1.

A minimal volume of demographic information was obtained from participants in order to maintain anonymity due to the small scale of the study. If the study was larger, additional demographic information could be collected on participant research background, non-HE work experience and research supervisory experience. The inclusion of more demographic attributes in a larger scale study would also allow for a potential synergy between qualitative and quantitative analysis, with the latter potentially enabling a deductive approach to findings (Goswami, 2011). For this introductory study however the demographic data collected was useful as a way of grouping findings.

Table 4.1 Demographic attributes of participants.

Demographic attributes		Count
Location	Netherlands	2
	United Kingdom	2
	Sweden	1
Role title	Director (or equivalent)	2
	Programme leader (or equivalent)	3
Research active	Yes	3
	No	2
Years working in promoting RI	3 - 5 years	3
	8 - 10 years	2

Codes and Themes

Ahead of data collection, the five a priori codes were: “Culture change”; “External agencies”; “Good research practice”; “Research misconduct” and “Shared learning environment”. Through an interpretative approach, the number of codes increased to a total of 27 codes supported by 266 unique references (text extracts only) from participants that could be used to address the study’s research questions and hypotheses. As summarised in Table 4.2, in total, participants’ contribution to codes ranged from 25 to 30 code contributions per participant, along with 48 to 84 references (inclusive of text extracts, along with memos and annotations) per participant.

Table 4.2 Summary of number of code contributions and references per participant.

Participant	No. of code contributions	No. of references*
1	28	66
2	29	54
3	25	48
4	30	84
5	26	59

* Totals 311 as inclusive of text extracts, along with memos and annotations.

Based on Thomas’ (2017) finding that a successful approach to mitigate against potential researcher positionality is to ask a question that may shape and guide the remainder of the interview, “What do you consider to be good research practice?” was the first question asked of participants after the control questions. Displayed in Figure 4.1, responses were as expected around research results being valid, reliable, open and transparent, along with practices being informed by policy and guidelines. An unexpected finding was how each participant first and foremost explicitly stated that good research practice is discipline specific. Discussion around discipline specific research practices and consistency in approach across units in HEIs ended up being a significant finding in an overarching theme presented later. This finding feeds into the importance of a leader of RI possessing an awareness of competent boundary spanning (Williams, 2002).

It is important to highlight that the entire semi-structured interview could have focussed on good research practices and what is considered to be these practices, hence the findings presented in Figure 4.1 are only initial inputs from participants that were built upon throughout the interview.

Figure 4.1 Summary of initial input from participants when asked the question “What do you consider to be good research practice?”

Notwithstanding that the question posed to participants was an initial question in the interviews, the responses align with the recent report by Chairelli et al. (2022) on behalf of UK Research and Innovation, Cancer Research UK and GuildHE on facets of RI.

The word frequency analysis approach outlined by Feng and Behar-Horenstein (2019) did not add any new information to the codes found through the interpretative approach. Removing the non-contributing word (Sarica and Luo, 2021) of “Research”, as displayed in the initial analysis in Figure 4.2, led to eight words encountered in the interviews (or their stemmed variant) with a weighted average of at least 0.5%, as displayed in Figure 4.3. (Word frequency analysis tables to complement Figure 4.2 and Figure 4.3 are in Appendix vii.)

When the text associated with the words highlighted (including stemmed variant) in Figure 4.3 were investigated in the transcripts, it was found that the words were mapped to either the a priori codes or emergent codes already. Even though the word frequency analysis did not produce any new findings, it turned out to be a useful mechanism to verify that nothing major was missed by the previous semantic coding method. Even with the words frequently used not bringing any new information, it was still interesting to find that according to the research participants, “practices” –

Figure 4.2 Initial word frequency analysis of most frequently occurring words, with a weighted percentage of at least 0.5%.

Figure 4.3 Word frequency analysis with stop-words approach implemented.

the actual doing of research - contributed towards the research culture, whether that is good research practices or QRPs. Also, the impact of the human capital - “people” and “researchers” - have on a culture in “institutions” was interesting to observe.

Axial coding followed isolating the 27 codes. This analysis yielded seven overarching themes, as summarised in Figure 4.4, with the mapping of codes to themes included in Appendix viii. Detailed discussion of the themes is included in the next chapter, but notably although the themes are aligned with the literature review what was a surprising finding was how prevalent “External Engagements” and “Reforming Research Assessment” were as themes. The latter being quite poignant given the recent publication of the document “Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment” by Science Europe et al. (2022). Furthermore, while a “Shared learning environment” was an a priori code, it was interesting to see how this was absorbed by an overarching theme on “Open Research Practices”, an aspect of research that is to the fore of recent national and international research agendas (European Commission, 2019; Department of Further and Higher Education, Research, Innovation and Science, 2022). Finally, an unexpected finding in a study relating to research culture in a HEI, was how research misconduct and QRPs were not the most prevalent reference from the interviews. While discussion in the interviews was dependent on the questions asked and interview structure, it was interesting to find in this small-scale exploratory study that it would appear participants’ lack of mentioning research misconduct would support the claim that RI is “much more than misconduct” as discussed in an editorial piece in Nature (Ed.) (2019,

Figure 4.4 Overarching themes from the semi-structured interviews complemented with the number of references to each theme.

p.1) on how the emphasis on research misconduct in terms of RI may be holding back the progression of research.

Research Questions and Hypotheses

In relation to the primary research question and underlying hypotheses, the findings show, while not called out explicitly, that participants believe collective leadership is needed to promote a positive research culture in HEIs, with the leadership attributes including an awareness of the importance of competent boundary spanning, being adaptive and allowing time for professional development. Participants mentioned that change is needed in terms of the research landscape and research assessment, with this change to be led by evidenced-based strategic thinking with all relevant stakeholders involved in the conversations and decisions. Of course, research participants were only from HEIs across three European countries, and although there is general alignment with responses from the dissertation and Chairelli et al. (2022) which included participants from North America, the findings cannot be conclusive globally and would be worth further research.

In relation to the secondary research question, there is supporting evidence around the need for open communication, shared learning, training, along with researchers being actively engaged with

external collaborators to promote a positive research culture in HEIs. While all participants seemed to be aware of what needs to be done in fostering a positive research culture in HEIs, they were also cognisant that time, limited infrastructure and internal opposition are clear obstacles to realise these changes.

Summary

The data analysis plan outlined in the Methodology chapter was successful in developing themes in the area of educational leadership and RI. Analysis in NVivo, complemented by multiple reviews of the interview transcripts, established 27 codes supported by 266 unique references. These codes when collated, using axial coding, formed seven overarching themes. While the overarching themes align with findings from the literature review, the surprising output was the ranking of themes based on references, with “External Engagements” and “Reforming Research Assessment” to the forefront. “Open Research Practices” was an emergent theme not picked up by the a priori codes, along with importance placed by participants on gathering data to form evidence-based practice at the early stage of leading RI, as grouped under the “Research and Professional Development in RI” theme.

The themes uncovered are very much dependent on questions asked in the interviews and overall interview structure, which may have changed if different questions were posed, or more time was spent exploring answers to particular questions. Nonetheless the findings are informative and may be useful in the initial steps to support institutes’ development of leadership in RI training and strategy in future. Discussion in the next chapter will weave through the findings in more detail, with support from participants’ quotes, along with comparisons to existing literature.

5. Discussion

In the previous chapter, seven overarching themes were identified for the purposes of exploring types of effective leadership models in promoting a positive research culture in HEIs. This chapter will provide depth and insight to these themes with discussion and supporting quotes from research participants underpinning findings presented in the previous chapter that should contribute to establishing evidence informed recommendations on leadership practices of RI. The discussion revolves around themes identified in the previous chapter, with a broad range of pressures intertwined in line with literature (Hargreaves and Fullan, 2012; Stoll et al., 2012; Mårtensson et al., 2016; Mowles et al., 2018; Robishaw et al., 2019; Labib et al., 2022). The overarching themes are presented in terms of how they may link to another, from the researcher perspective, as opposed to ranking by the number of references made in the interviews and summarised in Figure 4.4.

Leadership Practices and Culture Change

While seven themes are discussed, this first one gained the most attention during the interviews. This is largely due to question formulation, as this was the primary focus of the study, but there were interesting emergent findings within this area. As mentioned in the previous chapter and summarised in Figure 4.1, participants were clear that attributes to good research practices are discipline specific. This sentiment continued throughout each interview when discussing RI leadership practices with participants, where all participants were explicit that cognisance is required of the relationship between RI and how it may vary across disciplines. One participant stated they often experience incoherence and inconsistencies with HEI systems such that:

People have no clue where to go. Several departments are organising similar things and no one on the periphery understand who is responsible for what ... The other day I had a discussion with a colleague from my university and together we discovered that there are five handbooks and six websites basically providing the same content, but none of them completely complete. That's awful!

The discipline specific nature to RI foregrounds the importance of boundary spanning leadership as posited by Weick's (1976) and Pryor and Henley (2018), and being able to engage people across boundaries (Senge et al., 2014).

All participants mentioned there are challenges when engaging people across boundaries, where one participant mentioned the need to be “humble in approach” and offer advice based on personal perspective, but that there is a need to work together as “some things I can see that might help you, but you have to make the decision whether this is methodologically acceptable or not, in relation to your research question”. The same participant followed with “collegiality is a very important principle when it comes to how you lead [RI]”.

Time spent engaging peers and colleagues was mentioned by all participants, where one participant stated “the more granular you can do that and the more local to where they are you can do it, the better. Harder work, but it is better”. The same participant mentioned that if they were to start over they “would spend even more time talking to people. Investing and listening to them”. Another participant mentioned:

A labour intensive process that we put in place that I think paid dividends was actually to visit each department separately and basically discuss with them ... what good research looks like in your discipline and that bridged the gap between high level logically unassailable values that nobody is going to disagree with, with a demonstration that we are actually interested with how it looks on the ground, and that we are sympathetic to the fact that in some disciplines somethings count and some don't, but acknowledging that separating time for that discussion is necessary so that peoples thoughts can be collected and organised, and supporting some type of forward actions.

This quote from a participant again speaks to a leadership approach with awareness of competent boundary spanning (Williams, 2002), but also openness and communication as stated by Kania and Kramer (2011), Senge et al. (2014) and Labib et al. (2022).

Participants were asked how RI champion contributors (points of contact for questions around RI) across a HEI could be impactful on the research culture. One participant responded with:

The challenge in the research integrity champions is that you slightly miss out in all the other dimensions that might be needed around research integrity, for example, how to support careers, how to support open research and so on. The challenge there is how do you bring all these things together without making that role almost impossible.

This participant continued with saying that as opposed to a champion role, there is a need for a signposting role established first, with champion roles secondary. Signposting is different to champions in that it points the researcher towards where to get support on data management, authorship, ethical guidance, while champions would answer questions on dilemmas and issues relating to RI. As opposed to champions, the same participant advocated for a:

... collective or forum where you have experts in different parts of integrity – research practice, trusted research, open research, reproducibility, research for management, information compliance and that's where queries go. Because there will be people there that know different aspects and of course problems always sit in between. Integrity issues always sit in between...and by virtue of the forum and having all that expertise, where you have people that speak with each other to resolve an issue, there is the potential for people there to grow themselves to have a much broader understanding of integrity than any individual sitting out in a department might have.

The idea of a collective or forum was a point mentioned by four of the five participants in distributing responsibility for championing RI throughout a HEI. The concept of a forum is analogous to communities of learning mentioned by Kools and Stoll (2016), Murphy et al. (2006) and Kilpert et al. (2022) in creating a culture of collaboration and learning in educational settings. Furthermore, in Forsberg et al.'s (2018) consensus statement one of the thirteen key issues that should be addressed in fostering RI is establishing a RI committee within HEIs.

One participant mentioned while it is the responsibility of the researcher to follow good practices, it is the responsibility of the HEI leader to support them, aligning with recent findings from Evans et al.'s (2022) qualitative study on stakeholder experiences of RI. Another participant added that leadership of policy and training needs to be supported by a values-based framework. The point from this participant was that if HEI leaders can first agree a set of values to follow in RI and overall good research practice, the positive impact on the research culture follows. However, the biggest issue with deciding its values is "each institution does not have the luxury to make up its own rules...as they need to be linked in with funders, prize givers and other institutions". The influence of funders and other external agencies will be returned to later.

Values may be agreed upon based on mandates from external agencies or an evidence-based source, but aligned with Kotter (1996) participants felt the next step is to share the vision around the values and have “clarity of communication for the purposes of amplifying the agenda and approach”. Communicating a vision is a point regularly highlighted by both Kania and Kramer (2011) and Senge et al. (2014) in discussing successful collective leadership within a system.

All participants discussed at length the need to adapt to changes in the research culture including, but not limited to: acceptance of OR, open communication, reforming research assessment. One participant mentioned “a pressure and a strategic acknowledgment of the need to improve integrity and culture generally, for the long-term health of the research culture”. A challenge to adapting to change in culture mentioned by another participant is that some researchers have a closed mindset, not realising that just because “that's the way that the game used to be played ... it doesn't mean that's the way that the game is going to be played in future”. This was a sentiment corroborated by another participant, who added for this reason “change will be slow” which aligns with Murphy et al. (2006), Kania and Kramer (2011) and Senge et al.'s (2014) findings on how adaption to change and professional development should be self-sustaining within a system, allowing time for reflection and creative conversations.

Aligning with Kotter (1996) and potentially other change theorists (Lewin, 1947; Fullan, 2007) all participants regularly mentioned the importance of communicating what expectations are in a research context, including rigour, supporting careers, openness and other related points, while “behind that aligning our policies, our communications, our training, our evaluation”. The leadership challenge with change, called out in various guises by all participants is “embedding [change] in the day-to-day practices and structures so it is embedded in what they do, as opposed to something else to add to what they are doing already”. All participants stated that structures need to be fit for purpose in terms of infrastructure, both physical and digital, training and overall support in RI, aligning with Bubb and Earley (2013), Forsberg et al. (2018) and Casci and Adams (2020).

Infrastructure, Training and Support in RI

All participants agreed that in order for RI to become embedded in the research culture of a HEI, there needs to be the appropriate infrastructure, training and supports for the researcher. One participant speaks to distributed leadership to enable this:

There is no point on having a policy on research integrity and open research, if the library has not provided a platform, if the resources are not there, if the expertise are not there, if conversations are being had in parallel committees. So, it requires having a more joined up distributed leadership and less ownership of individual programmes.

This response speaks to the responsibility placed on the HEI analogous to the recent findings by Evans et al. (2022).

Two of the five participants explicitly mentioned that often for people within HEIs, the expertise to facilitate training on RI is lacking. Another participant added that within HEIs the “key colleagues in individual and department level are the individuals that do training”, with another participant stating that the training should be practical based and framed around:

How do you get a good publication? How do you get it noticed? How do you go from a research idea to identifying collaborators? How do you identify what the best outlet is for your research? Who do you go to, to ensure it has the highest degree of visibility? Where do you go for discussions on authorship and so on?

This response supports the work of Casci and Adams (2020), along with a blog by Nosek (2019) that a participant referenced in an interview in terms of a pyramid strategy for culture change, as presented in Figure 5.5. In Figure 5.5, it is stated that policy is required so that the researchers are aware of the HEI’s position on the topic, but then this needs to be supported by incentives that recognises the researchers work in good research practices around RI, OR and so on. A participant mentioned that “if it's not recognised, it's hard to see how do you get the buy in general, from supervisors or from students”. Nosek (2019) posits that incentives should then be supported by the aforementioned forums, in line with the literature by Kools and Stoll (2016) and Kilpert et al. (2022). The next layer in the pyramid is making the experience of training and learning about RI easy. One participant mentioned there is the need for the “appropriate expertise to ensure that compliance is

not only understood, but made easy”. In an educational leadership setting, this point aligns with Kools and Stoll (2016) when they state that a leader should have the capacity to present a problem in an understandable manner. Nosek (2019) concludes that the all these layers in culture change need to be supported by the appropriate infrastructure, as mentioned in the literature by Muczyk and Reimann (1987), Wilkinson et al. (2016) and Technological University Research Network (2019).

Figure 5.5 Strategy for Culture Change (Nosek, 2019).

Research and Professional Development in RI

Kania and Kramer (2011), Prysor and Henley (2018), Mejlgaard et al. (2020) and Science Europe, (2022) state that in order to adapt to changes in an educational and research culture setting, there needs to be buy-in from management. Observations made by two of the five participants from this study were that there is “minimal evidence of what works” when it comes to leadership in RI, and “when it comes to obtaining support from management there is a need to develop evidence-based practice”. These two participants mentioned the need for research and scholarship into what works in RI leadership. There needs to be a “community of research practice delivering evidence that works”. This echoes the forum mentioned by four of the five participants earlier.

One participant, when asked what they would do differently if starting over, stated they “would spend more time trying to get data”. They found that developing a research culture survey “proved to be really useful [and] we should have done it earlier”. This participant’s use of a survey is analogous to Guskey (2002) and Everard et al.’s (2004) approach of using surveys for monitoring the impact on organisation support and change, to measuring participants’ use of new knowledge skills

and overall motivation. One participant said that if they were in management and asked to change a process or procedure, they "wouldn't do that unless someone could show [them evidence] that it works" and this can only be achieved with research on what does and does not work in RI leadership.

When carrying out research to form the evidence base for a new initiative that may provide a mechanism for professional learning (Porritt et al., 2017) or professional development (Hargreaves, 2011), one participant mentioned that initiatives often failed when they were "not co-created with users, that [we]re not well tested, and prioritises administration over user friendliness". A PLC, as mentioned by Stoll et al. (2012), could be a useful avenue to pilot initiatives informally as "you only discover user friendliness and also comprehensibility when you test".

Time was also mentioned by all participants as being an obstacle in trying to develop professionally where "being a leader of a university, it's not easy to learn new things. You just have no time for it". However, with time, one participant called out

...the best thing to learn something is to teach about it, because then you have to delve in the topic. The best thing is to start reading a new article is to be a reviewer of it or in the assessment committee of the PhD students and when you are at the top of your university that's the only opportunity you have to pick up new things.

An interesting take from this participant's point was that they were leaning on professional development over professional learning in that you need to put the learning into practice and implement, analogous to positions by Earley and Porritt (2009) and Casci and Adams (2020) on professional development and implementation as opposed to professional learning.

One participant mentioned that the opportunities to stay informed with changes in the research landscape has become a lot easier with access to:

...newsletters from funding bodies, lobby groups and sectors, but also reading. There is a lot of literature now, including in the mainstream scientific and academic press. So, one can take advantage of there being a lot of editorials, commentaries around this.

Similar to Earley and Porritt (2009) and Bubb and Earley (2013), one participant outlined the need for provision in time and “opportunity within their position as support staff to educate themselves and keep up to date and engage in various ways that you can keep this very high level of competence.”

Open Research Practices

At the start of the dissertation OR was not in the scope, as it was not as prevalent as RI in the majority of the literature review. However, from the data analysis, there is no ignoring that OR is an emerging area, in parallel with RI, and warrants attention. All participants mentioned the importance of OR practices in terms of research culture with one participant saying that OR “methods are part and parcel of good research practices. They don't cover the complete grounds but pretty much a lot of it”, while another participant added if they were to start over in their work on RI, they would have “from the very beginning framed a lot of our work as sort of open and responsible research”.

The challenge with implementing OR practices, as mentioned by Wilkinson et al. (2016), is around ensuring HEIs have the necessary infrastructure to curate and store research outputs in accordance with the FAIR principles, which returns to Nosek’s (2019) point, as highlighted by a participant, on infrastructure (Muczyk and Reimann, 1987; Kania and Kramer, 2011). Three of the five participants felt that in principle no researcher is against OR, but whether or not there are the appropriate resources to support the practice is the real issue, which may depend on the HEI size, funds available to put structures in place, along with having the appropriate expertise in-house to show what good OR practices are and to “lead by example”.

In terms of this dissertation on leadership, the researcher has tried to follow through on good research practice throughout the life cycle of the study to date, from being open and transparent around the research ethical review (Appendices ii – iv), to outlining the thought process for the methodology (Chapter 3; Appendix i), having a DMP (Appendix v), sharing script used to generate figures (Appendix vi), along with all findings (Chapter 4, Appendices vii – viii), up to and including Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) and International Standard Book Numbers (ISBNs) for all references, where possible, to ensure access to references used in the dissertation are findable. Finally, the plan from the outset, as recommended by two of the five participants given the little evidence

available on leadership and RI, was to share the dissertation open access (University College London Discovery, 2022) and “in the form of a preprint for a later publication”.

Notwithstanding the requirement for the appropriate infrastructure to carry out research openly (Technological University Research Network, 2019; Haven et al., 2022), there can be some easy wins, for example, requiring all researchers to have an Open Researcher and Contributor ID (ORCID), so that each researcher can be uniquely identified in research outputs, to the use of Contributor Roles Taxonomy (CRediT) in publications to acknowledge contributors to research outputs (Moher et al. 2020). These are initial steps in OR that are not labour intensive and align with Chairelli et al.’s (2022) indicators of RI that should have a high feasibility for immediate action.

Although OR is seen as a key component to good research practice, two of the five participants highlighted that not all OR is good research, with one participant stating that:

...there is a danger there, of course, in that not all research that is open, is done with integrity. There is a hierarchy. Transparency makes it easier to evaluate integrity. A badly executed plan of work that is transparent isn't any better fundamentally.

This quote really speaks to the link between OR and RI, in that if a researcher shares poor research openly, then the openness of the methods and outputs enables the RI to be determined and any shortcomings highlighted (National Open Research Forum, 2019; Haven et al. 2022).

External Engagements

From the findings there were two main facets to external engagements. The first was external collaborations on research studies and communities of practices being analogous to JPDs mentioned by Kools and Stoll (2016). The second was engaging with external agencies’ demands and expectations around good research practice, which was also a priori code.

A surprising finding was the importance participants placed on external collaborations. In terms of external collaborations four of the five participants engage in some type of external learning community, where the overarching impression was that it is “a really good way of keeping up to

date and [have] an awareness of what's happening". One participant found engaging in JPDs a support of the day-to-day work as:

...it can be difficult for us in our role to have a certain conversation or informational exchange with another authority, but perhaps if we step in with another hat, as representatives of another organisation, different doors will open and it will be easier to have that type of conversation that we need to have.

Singh (2001), Mowles et al. (2018) and World Economic Forum (2019) mentioned how fast the research landscape is changing, but one participant was quick to highlight that the research landscape "is changing rapidly, but potentially from the more positive side it is converging from across the world" due to openness and accessibility of international good research practices. Singh (2001) describes this, not explicitly in research context but in an overarching HE context, as the "converging trends in higher education transformation".

Participants were all advocates of external collaborations, but three of the five highlighted the need to be involved in the decision making of external agencies as well, as this provides "direct insight into what is happening, as opposed to just being at the receiving end to what comes out of these bodies". All the participants mentioned the power of funding agencies, with one participant describing it as: "Funders say open access and that's what we do. Funders say open data, and that is what we do. Funders are much more powerful than the management of research institutions". The importance of being involved in these meetings with external agencies was so that issues around infrastructure, resources and training cannot be ignored when potential targets are being altered by the external agencies.

Two of the five participants mentioned the importance for the conversations that occur in the external meetings to be filtered down locally through respective HEIs, in line with Labib et al. (2022). Perhaps this is where the internal PLCs mentioned by Stoll et al. (2012) are key, where the learning from the external communication are shared through internal PLCs.

Research Misconduct, QRPs and Compliance

Nature (Ed.) (2019) stated that RI is much more than research misconduct, which in a certain way was evident in the findings from the dissertation in how references to “Research Misconduct, QRPs and Compliance” was not the most prevalent theme. One participant remarked that “people’s minds default to misconduct because to some extent that’s all there was. That is where it all started”, while in reality:

...no researcher goes to work on a Monday morning and sets out to do bad research. It is just that they end up doing research that is bad because of a variety of competing pressures. Sometimes it's that they don't have the training to do good research...Sometimes it is because of the expectation placed on them because of their institution, either directly in terms of this is what your annual target is, or what the institution requires of them for promotion or continuation of contract.

All participants agreed that research misconduct does happen but it is not as widespread as some may perceive, but that the wider issue is around QRPs. One participant mentioned that RI:

...has a lot more to it than just avoiding FFP. Trying to make people aware that the practices that have the biggest impact on the trustworthiness of science and not stealing and cheating and lying practices, it's the poor analysis practices. It's the not keeping records of what you're doing, it's stuff that is every day. It is the everyday mistakes and nobody is morally deficient because they do them. But maybe we are quite not aware of the impact of these as researchers.

Participants agreed that within the HEI research community there is not much negativity around research misconduct as the investigation of potential cases has to be conducted so confidentially that there is not a great awareness of even if it is operating. One issue mentioned in Forsberg et al.’s (2018) statement on working with RI is the need to increase transparency of misconduct cases. Three of the five participants believed that most researchers perceive that research misconduct “concerns others, other disciplines, other departments, but not them, not their group. So, it's just ignored, because it's not about them”. One participant mentioned that researchers are not looking for the problems either and that “there is poor monitoring. Usually no one is checking whether you are doing what you are supposed to do”.

Participants mentioned pressures around QRPs can often be time pressured where “in academia, people are over worked chronically nowadays...”, as supported by Hargreaves and Fullan (2012), Woolston (2019), Woolston (2020) and Ayres (2022), “...so everyone is trying to cut corners to save time and many inappropriate behaviours or even illegal [behaviours] will just help you to save time”, which leads to “suboptimal and not as productive processes, and that is awful because that is our main business, and then we do damage to institutional reputation”, (also see Robishaw et al., 2019; Evans et al., 2022).

All participants said it is essential to have communication of research misconduct procedures within HEIs. It was felt that with transparency around procedures, researchers will change. One participant noted that while changing “may not be costly financially, it is expensive in resource terms because we are asking people to change what they do” and so time is needed for this. There could be learnings here from creating a mechanism to “generate short term wins” (Kotter, 1996, p.23) in order to recognise success with change. Of course, this speaks to incentives for researchers to carry out good research practices in terms of RI and OR and other related areas, which forms an integral component of very recent discussions internationally on reforming research assessment.

Reforming Research Assessment

One participant captured the landscape quite succinctly on what research management, both internal and external to HEIs, has done “is taken [researchers] in a path where self-interest pays”. Although, this is not necessarily pleasant to think, when supported by another participant’s comment it is hard to ignore.

A very strong barrier is that we seem to have many inappropriate and even wrong and perverse incentives along the way. No one is giving you career points for doing the right thing, normally, and you get your career points mainly still for publishing a lot and being cited a lot and all the rest is a waste of time from that perspective, so getting the incentive right is really important.

One participant mentioned that one of the impacts of this current research culture around researcher assessment is the wellbeing of researchers, as reported by Woolston (2019) and Ayres (2022) in terms of PhD students, where “PhD students almost exclusively do their PhDs by publication” as opposed to acknowledgement of other research contributions and practices – e.g.,

using DMPs, sharing data openly, presenting at conferences, publishing in open access journals – instead it is predominately about publication, where “there's publication pressure for everyone, but I do think our PhD students are particularly under an awful lot of pressure”. The same participant added that even for staff, good research practices “has not reached a level of acknowledgement in terms of assessment for promotion or tenure”, where “we all know that people are valued more on the article that they produce, rather than other tasks such as teaching or supervision”.

In discussing research assessment, three of the five participants mentioned that in their HEI, they are trialling the narrative CV and using qualitative research assessment as mentioned in the recent report by Science Europe et al. (2022) on reforming research assessment. One participant mentioned that they welcomed the opportunity to pilot the concept, because what they find with these initiatives is that “when you try to implement them, they are not well developed”. Another participant whose HEI is not trialling the narrative CV felt that:

We need to carefully think about how to find a good balance, because it is also completely unrealistic to actually, evaluate researchers in any promotion process or hiring process on the basis of a qualitative assessment of the work, because the Committee will never have the time to read even 10% of the work of the top candidates.

What is clear is that reforming research assessment will take time, with the recent Science Europe et al. (2022) framework for change collecting signatories from September 2022.

Another participant mentioned that what they advise researchers in their HEI while they wait for new assessment procedures to become embedded, is to inform them that conversations are taking place and to try make them really aware that change is happening and of the “initiatives that are driving change, like, DORA, the Hong Kong Principles and Plan S in terms of what funders are going to be asking for and demanding”. Overall, participants are optimistic that change will happen and although Science Europe et al.'s (2022) framework was published after the interviews were carried out, Nature (Ed.) (2022) believes the recent agreement, if signed by HEIs, is a step in the right direction.

Summary

Five semi-structured interviews produced a large volume of data which enabled development of important themes around leadership practices and research culture. All participants spoke of engaging across boundaries consistently and openly as very important and were all similar in mindsets as to good research practices in terms of RI and OR impacting the research culture. It was interesting to note how discussion in the interviews were not led by research misconduct and QRPs, but more around the need for an open and fair framework for research assessment. Although participants were clear that OR and RI are not one in the same, it was interesting to note how frequent the two were spoken about and mentioned together throughout the interviews and subsequent findings and discussions, with OR clearly being an emerging area. Unsurprisingly all participants mentioned time as a big challenge when it comes to implementing good research practices, but more prevalent to time was that the work around good research practice is not formally recognised. An interesting emerging finding is how the sustainability of positive changes in a research culture is dependent on reforming research assessment and the leadership around this assessment.

6. Conclusions and Future Work

Research Questions and Hypotheses

This study's primary research question was: What type of leadership models do senior research leaders find most effective in promoting a positive research culture in HEIs? The first hypothesis stated that senior research leaders need to adapt their leadership style to respond to the regular changing of compliance and enhancement issues in HE research integrity, while the second hypothesis asserted that collective leadership is an appropriate approach to lead change to embed good research practices in the research culture.

Findings from the dissertation showed that the overarching leadership style to promote a positive research culture within HEIs was collective with adaptive and competent boundary spanning characteristics within a system, along with cognisance of the need for continuous professional development. In terms of the latter, there was compelling evidence of the positive impact of external engagement, both in engaging with external agencies and communities of practice and the need for learnings from these external engagements to be filtered through HEIs internally through forums, learning communities or newsletters. There was agreement among all participants that change in research culture is occurring and leaders need to adapt to these changes. Findings also outlined that in order for HEIs to be proactive as opposed to reactive to change, with support from management in terms of resourcing the appropriate infrastructure and training, that evidence-based research in collaboration with the future users is essential for the sustainability of change in the research culture.

This study's secondary research question was: What practices have senior research leaders found most effective in leading change and promoting a positive research culture in their HEI, in line with changing internal and external requirements? The third hypothesis stated that in order to overcome leadership obstacles to promoting good research practices, the wider research community should be involved in policy and procedure development.

Participants found collaboration and engagement with the research community both internal and external to HEIs to be effective in leading change, along with gathering research evidence regularly to inform decisions. Findings showed that outlining core values and principles at institutional level,

around expectations of good research practices is the initial step in promoting a positive research culture, but that the values and principles need to be subsequently supported by the necessary policies and training at various levels within the HEI. It was expected to find that RI would be seen as an integral component of a positive research culture, but what was surprising was how RI and OR were often mentioned together, although the study participants were clear that the two practices are not one and the same.

Limitations of the Research

The main limitation to the research study was the sample size was small with five participants across HEIs from three European countries. Rationale for the chosen approach was outlined in detail in the Methodology chapter including the paradigm of choice, research instrument and sample selection. Due to the small-scale nature of the study, it was important to maintain participant anonymity, hence little demographic information could be utilised. If the study was larger, additional demographic information could have been collected to potentially allow a synergy between qualitative and quantitative analysis, with the latter potentially enabling a deductive approach to findings.

A non-probability sampling method was used and as such had the potential for bias in findings, although the background of participants was different and they came from different jurisdictions. Nonetheless, if time allowed a probability sampling method would have been a preferred choice. Furthermore, the initial plan of including a representative from a HEI in Finland did not materialise, and as mentioned in the Methodology chapter this may have led to a missed opportunity of gaining additional insights into leadership practices and promoting a positive research culture from a country with many successful initiatives in promoting good research practice. Given the scale of the study, participants outside of Europe were precluded from participating, however expanding the study to include other participants in other continents would have enabled a comparative approach between European HEIs and non-European HEIs.

In the data analysis, when isolating codes a semantic approach was adopted based on the topic of leadership and RI being under-researched, thus yielding an overarching thematic description of the entire dataset (Braun and Clarke, 2006). A limitation to this type of analysis is that there is the

potential loss of the depth and complexity of the data, that latent coding would have enabled in terms of a more nuanced approach.

Recommendations for Future Research

This dissertation contributes to the under-researched topic of leadership in RI, however, there is potential to build on the research and include additional countries. As a matter of priority including Finland in an expansion of the study would be important, for reasons already mentioned. Also, with the recent declaration in France that they will require PhD students to take a research ethics oath as part of the research studies (Rabesandratana, 2022), it could prove insightful including France in a broader study, along with HEIs from other European countries. A broader European HEI based study would enable a potential synergy with Evans et al.'s (2022) findings.

With recent developments in the USA over the summer of 2022 in the government led publications demanding more rigour and transparency in research (United States Government Accountability Office, 2022) and requiring that all federally funded research studies must share their research findings openly and with no cost (Office of Science and Technology Policy, 2022), it could also prove insightful to include participants from HEIs in the USA in a broader study. This would potentially enable a comparative analysis with European countries, along with another potential synergy with the recently published results by Chairelli et al. (2022) on interviews with individuals from Europe, North America and the UK on facets of RI. Broadening the scope of the study to include countries with similar research cultures, along with dissimilar research cultures, could lead to an informative examination of global leadership practices to promote a positive research culture in HEIs and enable further grounded recommendations for practice.

Closing Remarks

A point made regularly in this dissertation is how rapidly the research landscape is changing (or converging as one participant eloquently phrased it). This was evident throughout the research study with the many new articles, blogs, editorials and manuscripts published in recent months, on RI, OR and other research culture related points. Potentially the most impactful publication was the "Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment" published in July 2022 by Science Europe et al. (2022). The agreement does bring hope for a change in research assessment and as such the

research culture in HEIs. With signatories being collected from September 2022, it is hoped that these will be quickly followed by implementation. As is evident from this dissertation's findings, implementation of some practices is a real challenge. Only time will tell of the impact the "Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment", but given the findings presented in this dissertation, it is clear that research assessment needs to change and some senior research leaders have the desire to drive change to promote a positive research culture in HEIs.

References

- Adams, W.C. (2015). 'Conducting Semi-Structured Interviews.' In Newcomer, K.E., Hatry, H.P. and Wholey J.S. (Eds.), *Handbook of Practical Program Evaluation* (4th Edition) Publisher: Jossey-Bass, pp. 492-505. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119171386.ch19>.
- All European Academies (2017). *European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity Revised Edition*, Berlin. ISBN: 978-3-00-055767-5.
- Ayres, Z. (2021). 'Five ways team leaders can improve research culture.' *Nature Reviews Materials* 6, 758–759 (2021). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41578-021-00357-1>.
- Barnett, A. and Gadd, E. (2022). 'University league tables have no legs to stand on.' *Significance*, 19: 4-7. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1740-9713.01663>.
- Bourke, B. (2014). 'Positionality: Reflecting on the Research Process.' *The Qualitative Report*, 19(33), 1-9. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.46743/2160-3715/2014.1026>.
- Brady, A. (2011). 'Opportunity Sampling'. In *The SAGE Dictionary of Social Research Methods*. London: SAGE Publications, p. 206. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.4135/9780857020116>.
- Braun, V. and Clarke V. (2006). 'Using thematic analysis in psychology.' In *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, Volume 3(2), pp. 77-101. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp0630a>.
- British Educational Research Association (2018). *Ethical Guidelines for Educational Research*, (4th Ed.). London. <https://www.bera.ac.uk/researchers-resources/publications/ethical-guidelines-for-educational-research-2018>.
- Brown, D., Taylor, C., Baldy, G., Edwards, G. and Oppenheimer, E. (1990). 'Computers and QDA - can they help it? A report on a qualitative data analysis programme.' *Sociological Review*, 38(1), pp. 134-150. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-954X.1990.tb00850.x>.
- Burnes, B. (2020). 'The Origins of Lewin's Three-Step Model of Change'. *The Journal of Applied Behavioral Science*, Vol. 56(1) 32-59. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0021886319892685>.
- Bubb, S. and Earley, P. (2013). *The use of training days: finding time for teachers professional development*, Educational Research, 55:3, 236-248. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131881.2013.825161>.
- Carley, K. (1993). 'Coding choices for textual analysis: A comparison of content analysis and map analysis'. *Sociological Methodology*, 23, 75-126. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2307/271007>.

- Carling, J. (2019). 'Research ethics and research integrity.' *MIGNEX Handbook* Chapter 4 (v1). Oslo: Peace Research Institute Oslo. Available at www.mignex.org/d013.
- Casci, T. and Adams, E. (2020). 'Research Culture: Setting the right tone.' *eLife*, 9:e55543. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.55543>.
- Chairelli, A., Johnson, R. and Loffreda, L. (2022). 'Executive Summary – Indicators of Research Integrity: An initial exploration of the landscape, opportunities and challenges.' *Zenodo*. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6827713>.
- Coghlan, D. and Brydon-Miller, M. (2014). 'Positionality'. In *The SAGE encyclopedia of action research*. SAGE Publications Ltd, pp. 628 – 628. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.4135/9781446294406.n277>.
- Connolly, M. (2016). 'Selecting Appropriate Research Methods for an Educational Context'. In Palaiologou, I., Needham, D. and Male, T. (Eds.), *Doing Research in Education*. London: SAGE Publications, pp. 136-155. ISBN: 978-1446266748.
- Corbin, J. and Strauss, A. (1990). 'Grounded theory research: Procedures, canons, and evaluative criteria'. *Qualitative Sociology*, 13, 3-21. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00988593>.
- Corlett, S. and Mavin, S. (2018). 'Reflexivity and Researcher Positionality'. In Cassell, C., Cunliffe, A. & Grandy, G. (Eds.) *The SAGE Handbook of Qualitative Business and Management Research Methods*, London: SAGE Publications. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.4135/9781526430212.n23>.
- Curry, S., de Rijcke, S., Hatch, A., Pillay, D. (G.), van der Weijden, I. and Wilsdon, J. (2020). *The changing role of funders in responsible research assessment: progress, obstacles and the way ahead* (RoRI Working Paper No.3). Research on Research Institute. Report. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.13227914.v2>.
- Cummings, S., Bridgman, T. and Brown, K. G. (2016). 'Unfreezing change as three steps: Rethinking Kurt Lewin's legacy for change management.' *Human Relations*, 69(1), 33–60. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0018726715577707>.
- Declaration on Research Assessment (2012). *San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment*. Available at: <https://sfedora.org/read/> (Accessed: 10 September 2022).
- Department of Further and Higher Education, Research, Innovation and Science (2022). *Impact 2030 – Ireland's Research and Innovation Strategy*. Dublin.

Digital Curation Centre (2005). *DMPOnline*. Available at: <https://dmponline.dcc.ac.uk/> (Accessed: 20 August 2022).

Earley, P. and Porritt, V. (2009). *Effective Practices in CPD, Final Report to the TDA*. London: Institute of Education.

Easton, L.B. (2008). 'From Professional Development To Professional Learning.' *Phi Delta Kappan*, 89(10), 755-761. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1177/003172170808901014>.

Elken, M. and Vukasovic, M. (2019). 'The Looseness of Loose Coupling: The Use and Misuse of "Loose Coupling" in Higher Education Research.' In J. Huisman and M. Tight (Ed.), *Theory and Method in Higher Education Research* (Vol. 5, pp. 53-71): Emerald Publishing Limited. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1108/S2056-375220190000005005>.

Else, H. (2021). 'Swedish research misconduct agency swamped with cases in first year'. *Nature*, 597, 461. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-021-02451-4>.

European Association of Research Management and Administration (1995). *EARMA Institutional Membership*. Available at: <https://earma.wildapricot.org/EARMA-Institutional-Members/?tab=2> (Accessed: 20 March 2022).

European Commission (2019). *Open Science*. Research and Innovation. Glinos, K. (editor), Publications Office.

European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Baker, L., Cristea, I., Errington, T., et al. (2020). *Reproducibility of scientific results in the EU: scoping report*, Lusoli, W.(editor), Publications Office. DOI: <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/341654>.

European Network of Research Integrity Offices (2008). *About ENRIO*. c/o Finnish National Board on Research Integrity TENK. Available at: <http://www.enrio.eu/about-enrio/> (Accessed: 07 March 2022).

Evans, N., Buljan, I., Valenti, E. et al. (2022). 'Stakeholders' Experiences of Research Integrity Support in Universities: A Qualitative Study in Three European Countries.' *Science and Engineering Ethics*, 28, 43. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11948-022-00390-5>.

Everard, K., Morris, G. and Wilson, I. (2004). 'Motivating people. In *Effective school management*'. *SAGE Publications Ltd*, pp. 25-45. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.4135/9781446211427.n3>.

Faraci, P., Lock, M. and Wheeler, R. (2013). 'Assessing leadership decision-making styles: psychometric properties of the Leadership Judgement Indicator.' *Psychology Research and Behavior Management*. 6:117- 123. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2147/PRBM.S53713>.

Feng, X. and Behar-Horenstein, L. (2019). 'Maximizing NVivo Utilities to Analyze Open-Ended Responses.' *The Qualitative Report*, 24(3), pp. 563-571. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.46743/2160-3715/2019.3692>.

Fielding, M., Bragg, S., Craig, J., Cunningham, I., Eraut, M., Gillinson, S., Horne, M., Robinson, C. and Thorp, J. (2005). *Factors Influencing the Transfer of Good Practice*. DfES Research Report RR615, Falmer, University of Sussex. ISBN: 1 84478 393 6.

Finnish Advisory Board on Research Integrity (2021). *Responsible Conduct of Research (RCR)*. Available at <https://tenk.fi/en/research-misconduct/responsible-conduct-research-rcr> (Accessed: 03 September 2022).

Forsberg, E.M., Anthun, F.O., Bailey, S. et al. (2018). 'Working with Research Integrity—Guidance for Research Performing Organisations: The Bonn PRINTEGER Statement.' *Sci Eng Ethics* 24, 1023–1034. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11948-018-0034-4>.

Fullan, M. (2007). 'Causes and Processes of Initiation.' In *The New Meaning of Educational Change*. Fourth Edition. Teachers College Press, pp. 64-83. ISBN: 978-0-8077-4765-0.

Goddard, W. and Melville, S. (2001). *Research Methodology: An Introduction* (2nd Ed.). Johannesburg, 2196, South Africa: Juta and Company. ISBN: 9780702156601.

Goertz, G. and Mahoney, J. (2012). 'Concepts and measurement: Ontology and epistemology.' *Social Science Information*. 51(2), pp. 205-216. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0539018412437108>.

Goswami, U. (2011). 'Inductive and deductive reasoning.' In U. Goswami (Ed.), *The Wiley-Blackwell handbook of childhood cognitive development*. Wiley-Blackwell, pp. 399–419. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781444325485.ch15>.

Guskey, T.R. (2002). *Does It Make a Difference? Evaluating Professional Development*, Educational, School, and Counseling Psychology Faculty Publications. https://uknowledge.uky.edu/edp_facpub/7.

Hallinger, P. (2005). 'Instructional Leadership and the School Principal: A Passing Fancy that Refuses to Fade Away'. *Leadership and Policy in Schools*, 4, 1-20. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/15700760500244793>.

Hallinger, P. and Heck, R. (1997). 'Exploring the Principal's Contribution to School Effectiveness: 1980 - 1995'. *School Effectiveness and School Improvement*, 9(2), 157-191. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/0924345980090203>.

Ham, C. (2015) 'Foreword', in Timmins, N. (Ed.) *The practice of system leadership: Being comfortable with chaos*. London: The King's Fund. ISBN: 978 1 909029 50 7.

Hanan, A.A. (2006). 'A View from Somewhere: Explaining the Paradigms of Educational Research.' *Journal of Philosophy of Education*, Vol. 40, No. 2, pp. 205-221. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9752.2006.00502.x>.

Hanover Research (2014). *Building a Culture of Research: Recommended Practices*. Academy Administration Practice. Washington DC. <https://www.hanoverresearch.com/media/Building-a-Culture-of-Research-Recommended-Practices.pdf>.

Hargreaves, A. and Fullan, M. (2012), "Stereotypes of Teaching" *Professional Capital: Transforming Teaching in Every School* Teachers College Press, pp. 24-45. ISBN: 978-0-8077-5332-3.

Hargreaves, D.H. (2011), *Leading a self-improving school system*, Nottingham, National College for School Leadership.

Haven, T., Gopalakrishna, G., Tjink, J., van der Schot, D. and Bouter, L. (2022). 'Promoting trust in research and researchers: How open science and research integrity are intertwined.' *MetaArXiv*, Preprint, viewed 13 August 2022. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.31222/osf.io/ngt3p>.

Heifetz, R., Kania, J. and Kramer, M. (2004). 'Leading Boldly.' *Stanford Social Innovation Review*, 2(3), 20-31. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.48558/T9XW-N926>.

Hicks, D., Wouters, P., Waltman, L. et al. (2015). 'Bibliometrics: The Leiden Manifesto for research metrics.' *Nature*, 520, 429-431. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/520429a>.

Higher Education Authority (2020). *Principles of Good Practice in Research in Irish Higher Education Institutions*. Dublin.

- Holmes, A. and Darwin, G. (2020). 'Researcher Positionality – A Consideration of Its Influence and Place in Qualitative Research – A New Researcher Guide.' *Shanlax International Journal of Education*, Vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 1-10. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.34293/education.v8i4.3232>.
- Horbach, S.P.J.M., Bouter, L.M., Gaskell, G., Hiney, M., Kavouras, P., Mejlgaard, N., et al. (2022). 'Designing and implementing a research integrity promotion plan: Recommendations for research funders.' *PLoS Biology* 20(8): e3001773. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3001773>.
- Horizon Europe (2021). *European Union Grants: Higher Education Programme Guide*. Version 1.4, pp. 38-54.
- House, R.J. (1971). 'A Path Goal Theory of Leader Effectiveness.' *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 16(3), 321-339. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2307/2391905>.
- House, R.J. and Mitchell, T.R. (1974). 'Path-goal theory of leadership.' *Journal of Contemporary Business*, 3: 1-97. DOI: [10.12691/education-5-7-2](https://doi.org/10.12691/education-5-7-2).
- Hox, J.J. and Boeijs, H.R. (2005). 'Data Collection, Primary vs. Secondary.' In *Encyclopedia of Social Measurement* (pp. 593-599). Amsterdam: Elsevier. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/B0-12-369398-5/00041-4>.
- Irish University Association (2021). *Irish Universities Association: Research Funding*. Available at: <https://www.iua.ie/for-researchers/research-funding/> (Accessed: 10 February 2022).
- Jackson, K. M. and Trochim, W. M. (2002). 'Concept mapping as an alternative approach for the analysis of open-ended survey responses.' *Organizational Research Methods*, 5(4), pp. 307-336. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1177/109442802237114>.
- Janis, I.L. (1972). *Victims of groupthink; a psychological study of foreign-policy decisions and fiascoes*. Boston, Houghton, Mifflin. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2307/3791464>.
- Jones, R.E. and Abdelfattah, K.R. (2020). 'Virtual Interviews in the Era of COVID-19: A Primer for Applicants.' *Journal of Surgical Education*, Volume 77, Issue 4, pp. 733-734. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsurg.2020.03.020>.
- Kania, J. and Kramer, M. (2011). 'Collective Impact.' *Stanford Social Innovation Review*, 9(1), 36–41. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.48558/5900-KN19>.

- Kilpert, L., Anyadi, S., Wozniak, M., Matthews, H. and Bultoc, D. (2022). 'Communities of practice: fostering a sense of community in complex organisations (a What Works case study).' AdvanceHE, London.
- Kivunja, C., and Kuyini, A.B. (2017). 'Understanding and Applying Research Paradigms in Educational Contexts.' *International Journal of Higher Education*, Vol 6, No 5, pp. 26 – 41. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5430/ijhe.v6n5p26>.
- Kools, M. and Stoll, L. (2016). 'What Makes a School a Learning Organisation?'. *OECD Education Working Papers*, No. 137, OECD Publishing, Paris.
- Kotter, J.P. (1996). *Leading Change*. Boston: Harvard Business School Press. ISBN: 978-1422186435.
- Labib, J., Tjink, J., Sijtsma, K., Bouter, L., Evans, N. and Widdershoven, G. (2022). 'How to combine rules and commitment in fostering research integrity?' *MetaArXiv*, Preprint, viewed 28 July 2022. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.31222/osf.io/sx58q>.
- Leithwood, K. (1994). 'Leadership for school restructuring'. *Educational Administration Quarterly*, 30, 498-518. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013161X94030004006>.
- Leithwood, K., Harris, A. and Hopkins, D. (2008). 'Seven strong claims about successful school leadership.' *School Leadership and Management*, 28 (1): 27-42. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13632430701800060>.
- Lester, J.N., Cho, Y. and Lochmiller, C.R. (2020). 'Learning to Do Qualitative Data Analysis: A Starting Point.' *Human Resource Development Review*. 19(1), pp. 94 - 106. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1534484320903890>.
- Lewin, K. (1947). 'Frontiers in group dynamics: Concept, method and reality in social science; social equilibrium and social change'. *Human Relations*, 1(1), 5-41. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1177/001872674700100103>.
- Male, T. (2016). 'Analysing Qualitative Data'. In I. Palaiologou, D. Needham and T. Male (Eds). *Doing Research in Education: Theory and Practice*. London: Sage Publications, pp. 177-191. ISBN: 978-1446266748.
- Malterud, K., Siersma, V.D. and Guassora, A.D. (2016) 'Sample Size in Qualitative Interview Studies: Guided by Information Power.' *Qualitative Health Research*, 26(13):1753-1760. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1049732315617444>.

Mårtensson, P., Fors, U., Wallin, S.B., Zander, U. and Nilsson, G.H. (2016). 'Evaluating research: A multidisciplinary approach to assessing research practice and quality.' *Research Policy*, Volume 45, Issue 3, pp. 593-603. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2015.11.009>.

MAXQDA (2021). *Stop word lists: improving visualization of text data*. Available at: <https://www.maxqda.com/blogpost/stop-word-lists> (Accessed: 26 August 2022).

Mejlgaard, N. Bouter, B. Gaskell, G. et al. (2020). 'Research integrity - nine ways to move from talk to walk'. *Nature*, 586, 358-360. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-020-02847-8>.

Moher, D., Bouter, L., Kleinert, S., Glasziou, P., Sham, M.H., Barbour, V, et al. (2020). 'The Hong Kong Principles for assessing researchers: Fostering research integrity.' *PLoS Biol*, 18(7): e3000737. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3000737>.

Mowles, C., Filosof, J., Andrews, R., Flinn, K., James, D., Mason, P. and Culkin, N. (2018). *Transformational Change in the Higher Education Sector: An inquiry into leadership practice*, AdvanceHE, London.

Murphy, J., Elliott, S., Goldring, E. and Porter, A. (2006). *Learning-Centered Leadership: A Conceptual Foundation*. The Wallace Foundation, Nashville.

Muczyk, J. and Reimann, B. (1987). 'The Case for Directive Leadership.' *The Academy of Management Executive*, 1(4), 301-311. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5465/ame.1987.4275646>.

National Open Research Forum (2019). *National Framework on the Transition to an Open Research Environment*. Report to Innovation 2020 Implementation Group. Dublin. DOI: <https://repository.dri.ie/catalog/0287dj04d>.

National Research Integrity Forum (2019). *National policy statement on Ensuring Research Integrity in Ireland*, Dublin.

National Research Integrity Forum (2022). *Framework to Enhance Research Integrity in Research Collaborations*, Dublin.

Nature (Ed.) (2019). 'Research integrity is much more than misconduct.' *Nature*, 570, 5. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-019-01727-0>.

Nature (Ed.) (2022). 'Support Europe's bold vision for reforming research assessment.' *Nature*, 607, 636. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-022-02037-8>.

- Neill, U.S. (2008). 'Publish or perish, but at what cost?' *J Clin Invest*, 118(7):2368-2368. <https://doi.org/10.1172/JCI36371>.
- Neylon, C. (2022). 'Stop misusing data when hiring academics.' *Nature*, 607, 637. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-022-02038-7>.
- Nosek, B. (2019). *Strategy for Culture Change*. Available at: <https://www.cos.io/blog/strategy-for-culture-change> (Accessed: 09 September 2022).
- O'Shea, T. (2013). *Essential Statistics for Researchers*. ISBN: 9780957505902.
- Office of Science and Technology Policy (2022). *Ensuring Free, Immediate, and Equitable Access to Federally Funded Research*. Executive Office of the President. United States of America.
- Orton, J. and Weick, K. (1990). 'Loosely coupled systems: A reconceptualization.' *The Academy of Management Review*, 15 (2), 203-223. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2307/258154>.
- Oxford Dictionary (2011). *Concise Oxford English Dictionary* (12th Ed.). Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Palaiologou, I., Needham, D. and Male, T. (2016). *Doing Research in Education*. London: Sage Publications. ISBN: 978-1446266748.
- Palinkas, L.A., Horwitz, S.M., Green, C.A., Wisdom, J.P., Duan, N. and Hoagwood, K. (2015). 'Purposeful Sampling for Qualitative Data Collection and Analysis in Mixed Method Implementation Research.' *Administration and policy in mental health*, 42(5), 533–544. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10488-013-0528-y>.
- Patton, M.Q. (1990). *Qualitative evaluation and research methods* (2nd Ed.). Newbury Park: Sage Publications. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/nur.4770140111>.
- Porritt, V., Spence-Thomas, K. and Taylor, C. (2017). *Leading Professional Learning and Development*. In: Earley, P. and Greany, T., (eds.) *School Leadership and Education System Reform*. Bloomsbury Academic: London, UK. ISBN: 9781474273954.
- Pryor, D. and Henley, A. (2018). 'Boundary spanning in higher education leadership: identifying boundaries and practices in a British university.' *Studies in Higher Education*, 43:12, 2210-2225. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2017.1318364>.
- QSR International Pty Ltd. (2020). *NVivo* (released in March 2020), <https://www.qsrinternational.com/nvivo-qualitative-data-analysis-software/home>.

Quality and Qualifications Ireland (2020). *Ireland's Framework of Good Practice for Research Degree Programmes*, Dublin.

R Core Team (2022). 'R: A language and environment for statistical computing.' *R Foundation for Statistical Computing*, Vienna, Austria. <https://www.R-project.org/>.

Rabesandratana, T. (2022). 'France will require Ph.D.s to take a research ethics oath'. *Science*, Vol 377, Issue 6603. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.add9092>.

Rawat, S. and Meena, S. (2014). 'Publish or perish: Where are we heading?' *Journal of research in medical sciences: the official journal of Isfahan University of Medical Sciences*, 19(2), 87–89. PMC3999612.

Research Prioritisation Steering Group (2018). *Research Priority Areas 2018 to 2023*. Innovation and Investment Division, Dublin.

Robishaw, J.D., DeMets, D.L., Wood, S.K., Boiselle, P.B. and Hennekens, C.H. (2019). 'Establishing and Maintaining Research Integrity at Academic Institutions: Challenges and Opportunities.' *The American Journal of Medicine*, Volume 133, Issue 3, Pages 87-90. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amjmed.2019.08.036>.

Räsänen, L. and Moore, E. (2016). 'Critical evaluation of the guidelines of the Finnish Advisory Board on Research Integrity and of their application.' *Research Integrity and Peer Review* 1, 15. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41073-016-0020-9>.

Sang, K.J.C. and Sitko, R. (2015). 'Chapter 8 Qualitative Data Analysis Approaches' In: O'Gorman, K.D. and MacIntosh, R. (ed) *Oxford: Goodfellow Publishers*. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.23912/978-1-910158-51-7-2775>.

Sarica, S. and Luo, J. (2021). 'Stopwords in technical language processing.' *PLoS ONE* 16(8): e0254937. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0254937>.

Science Europe (2015). *Briefing Paper on Research Integrity: What it Means, Why it Is Important and How we Might Protect it*. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5060051>.

Science Europe. (2021). *Empowering researchers with a thriving research system integrated in society*. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5726893>.

Science Europe (2022). *Position Statement: A Values Framework for the Organisation of Research*. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6637848>.

Science Europe, European University Association and Stroobants, K. (2022). *Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment*.

Senge, P., Hamilton, H. and Kania, J. (2014). 'The dawn of system leadership'. *Stanford Social Innovation Review*. 13(1), 27–33. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.48558/YTE7-XT62>.

Singh, M. (2001). 'Re-Inserting the "Public Good" into Higher Education Transformation', *Kagisano Higher Education Discussion Series*, 1: 8-18. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.18820/9781928357056/01>.

Standard Operating Procedures for Research Integrity (2019). *SOPs4RI Grant agreement ID: 824481*. DOI: [10.3030/824481](https://doi.org/10.3030/824481).

Stoll, L., Harris, A. and Handscomb G. (2012). *Great professional development which leads to great pedagogy: nine claims from research*, Nottingham, National College for School Leadership.

Department of Education and Skills (2011). *National Strategy for Higher Education to 2030*. Report of the Strategy Group, Ireland.

Technological Universities Research Network (2019). *Technological Universities - Connectedness & Collaboration through Connectivity*. Report to the Department of Education and Skills, Ireland.

Thomas, G. (2017). *How to do your Research Project*, 3rd ed., London: Sage Publications. ISBN: 978-1473948877.

United States Government Accountability Office (2022). *Research Reliability - Federal Actions Needed to Promote Stronger Research Practices*. Report to the Ranking Member, Committee on Commerce, Science, and Transportation, U.S. Senate. GAO-22-104411.

University College London (2011). *Records Management Policy*. Library Committee, London.

University College London (2020). *Research Data Policy*. Research Information and IT Services Group, London.

University College London Discovery (2022). *UCL Discovery*. Available at: <https://discovery.ucl.ac.uk/> (Accessed: 26 August 2022).

Weick, K. (1976). 'Educational organizations as loosely coupled systems.' *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 21(10), 1-19. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2307/2391875>.

Wellcome Trust (2020). *What Researchers Think About the Culture They Work In*. London.

- Wickham, H (2016). 'ggplot2: Elegant Graphics for Data Analysis.' *Springer-Verlag New York*. ISBN 978-3-319-24277-4, <https://ggplot2.tidyverse.org>.
- Wilkinson, D. and Birmingham, P. (2003). *Using Research Instruments: A Guide for Researchers* (1st Ed.). Routledge. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203422991>.
- Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. (2016). 'The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship'. *Scientific Data* 3, 160018. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>.
- Williams, P. (2002). 'The competent boundary spanner.' *Public Administration*, 80 (1), pp. 103-124. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9299.00296.UK>.
- Woolston, C. (2019). 'PhDs: the tortuous truth.' *Nature*, 575, 403-406. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-019-03459-7>.
- Woolston, C. (2020). 'Postdocs under pressure: "Can I even do this any more?".' *Nature*, 587, 689-692, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-020-03235-y>.
- World Economic Forum (2019). *This is why universities need strong strategic leadership*. Available at: <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2019/11/universities-need-excellent-strategic-leadership-here-s-what-it-looks-like/> (Accessed: 10 August 2022).

Appendices

Appendix i. Initial Interview Schedule

Introduction

- Confirm receipt of consent form.
- Reiterating information on anonymity and data storage.
- Explain why this topic has been chosen.
- Details on interview: length, notes, request permission to record.
- Reiterate questions can be skipped if needed, along with the right to withdraw at any point.
- Confirm that it is okay to commence?

Control questions

1. Can you please confirm your role title?
2. How long have you been in the current role? Or working in areas relating to current role?
3. In your current role, do you have time to carry out research of your own?

Theme 1 – Compliance and enhancement issues in Higher Education research

4. What do you consider to be good research practice?
5. What do you see as compliance and enhancement issues in Higher Education research in your HEI?
6. How do you stay up to date with compliance and enhancement issues in Higher Education research?
7. Where are the pressures for these issues coming from?
8. What are the repercussions if these issues are not addressed?
9. How do you approach addressing these issues internally?

Theme 2 – Leadership obstacles to promoting good research practices

10. How would you describe your approach to leading your area to promote good research practices?
11. What are the obstacles, if any, you encountered in your leadership in promoting good research practices?
12. Are there initiatives that were particularly successful in promoting good research practices? Why do you think these initiatives worked?
13. Are there initiatives that were not successful in promoting good research practices? Why do you think these initiatives did not work?
14. Do you incentivise good research practices at your institution? If yes, how do you? If no, are there reasons for not?

Theme 3 – Procedures around research misconduct

15. How do you handle alleged cases of research misconduct?
16. Do you have different procedures for addressing research misconduct for students and for staff?
17. In relation to disciplinary procedures for staff research misconduct, who did you engage with to develop the procedures in addressing alleged cases of research misconduct?
18. What impact do you think research misconduct procedures have on the culture and perceptions of research integrity at your institution?

Theme 4 – Leading change to embed good research practices in the research culture

19. How did you approach embedding good research practices in the research culture in your HEI?
20. How have you distributed responsibility for championing research integrity throughout the institution?
21. If you were to start over in designing and leading interventions around research integrity at your institution, is there anything different that you might do?

Closing

- Explain timeline for forwarding interview transcription for data validation.
- Confirm that a copy of final results will be shared after submission of the dissertation.

Appendix ii. Ethics Approval Letter

Institute of Education

Ethics Approval 2022

Ref: Examining international leadership practices to promote a positive research culture in Higher Education Institutes.

Date: 28 March 2022

Dear Seán,

I am pleased to notify your ethics application has been approved. Please make sure a copy of this letter is included as an appendix in your final submission.

You may now start your research for your MBA dissertation. If, however, you decide to change your approach you should consult with your supervisor.

May I wish you every success as you take the dissertation towards completion.

Best wishes,

Dr Trevor Male
UCL Centre for Educational Leadership.

Appendix iii. Information Leaflet

Dear [REDACTED],

My name is Seán Lacey and I would like to invite you to participate in my research study, 'Examining international leadership practices to promote a positive research culture in Higher Education Institutes'. I am currently studying for an MBA in Educational Leadership (International) at the University College London (UCL) Institute of Education and this research is being undertaken for my final dissertation as part of this programme. I also work full time at Munster Technological University (MTU), Ireland, as the Research Integrity & Compliance Officer, and motivation for this study has come about as a result of my recent appointment to this role with the responsibility of fostering a research environment that promotes the responsible conduct of research which maintains the highest standards of integrity.

The research study is a small-scale exploratory study that aims to use data gathered in interviews, with senior research leaders in Higher Education Institutes (HEIs) across Europe, to examine the leadership practices in relation to implementing research integrity policies and procedures, to establish effective approaches to promoting a positive research culture in HEIs. Before you decide about whether or not you wish to take part, it is important for you to understand why this research study is being carried out and what it will involve. Please take time to read the information provided below carefully and discuss the research study with other people if you wish.

On page 2, you will be informed about what the study is about and what participants are asked to do if they decide to take part. On page 3, you will be provided with specific, technical details on how the information you provide in the interviews will be collected, analysed and safely stored. You will also be provided information on how you can withdraw from the study, with my contact information for same. The consent form is on page 4.

If you would like any additional information on this research study, please do not hesitate to contact me by email by [REDACTED].

Kind regards,

[REDACTED]

Seán Lacey, BSc, PhD

UCL Centre for Educational Leadership

[REDACTED]

Study Overview

Study Title: Examining international leadership practices to promote a positive research culture in Higher Education Institutes.

What is this study about? This study aims to examine the leadership practices in relation to implementing research integrity policies and procedures, to establish effective approaches to promoting a positive research culture in Higher Education Institutes (HEIs).

Why is this study important? From the data obtained from the interviews, I aim to posit a series of evidence informed recommendations on leadership practices of research integrity to promote a positive research culture in HEIs, which can be applied in Ireland and other European contexts.

What will be required of me if I agree to participate? I would like to undertake one interview with you, of approximately 60 minutes in duration. This will take place remotely via Microsoft Teams or Zoom. Questions will cover some information for control purposes, along with questions relating to four themes:

1. Compliance and enhancement issues in Higher Education research.
2. Leadership obstacles to promoting good research practices.
3. Procedures around research misconduct.
4. Leading change to embed good research practices in the research culture.

Will anyone know you have been involved? I will not disclose the details of participants as part of this study and will anonymise all responses. The research population was identified as 50 HEIs, and I will interview no more than a 10% sample to maintain anonymity. The results overview shared with participants will be thematic and not contain any personal data.

Could there be problems if you take part? I do not plan to discuss any sensitive issues as part of this study, however, if you choose to participate you will be entitled to skip a question and/or stop the interview at any time should you feel uncomfortable and/or not wish to answer.

What will happen to the results of the research? This research will be used in my final dissertation which counts towards completion of the MBA in Educational Leadership (International). The final document will be published within the UCL research repository. Data gathered will be analysed using NVivo. The reporting of data gathered will not be concerned with individual responses as responses will be aggregated to deliver information organised by emerging themes. Where it is necessary to include quotes from individuals to support findings, quotes will be anonymised to ensure that the rights of the individual are respected and that the individual remains anonymous, with any specific identifying characteristics and personal data redacted. Data will be stored securely on a cloud-based drive within the UCL system for no more than twelve months following completion of the study. I will send a thematic overview of results to all participants who wish to see it. Results from the research study may be shared at a conference and/or in peer-reviewed publications.

Do you have to take part? There are no consequences for any individual who wishes to read the invitation letter, information leaflet and consent form and decide to not take part in the study.

Can I change my mind and withdraw from the research? Yes, you are under no obligation to take part in this study. It is your own choice to agree to participate.

Is there a specific time that I need to withdraw consent? You can stop the interview at any point without explanation. Shortly after the interview concludes, I will share your individualised interview transcript. Following sharing of your individualised interview transcript, you may choose to withdraw the information you have shared up to two weeks afterwards.

What happens when I withdraw from the research? All of your data will be destroyed and will not be included for the purpose of data analysis.

Data Protection Privacy Notice: The data controller for this study will be University College London (UCL). The UCL Data Protection Office provides oversight of UCL activities involving the processing of personal data, and can be contacted at data-protection@ucl.ac.uk. UCL's Data Protection Officer can also be contacted at data-protection@ucl.ac.uk. Further information on how UCL uses participant information can be found here: <https://www.ucl.ac.uk/legal-services/privacy/uclgeneral-research-participant-privacy-notice>.

The legal basis that will be used to process your personal data is performance of a task in the public interest. I will not be asking for any special category personal data. Your personal data will be processed so long as it is required for the research study, and will be held for a maximum of twelve months following completion of the study. I will pseudonymise the personal data you provide and will endeavour to minimise the processing of personal data wherever possible. If you are concerned about how your personal data is being processed, or if you would like to contact UCL about your rights, please contact UCL in the first instance at data-protection@ucl.ac.uk.

Contact for further information: If you have any questions before deciding whether or not to participate, please contact me on the following details: Dr Seán Lacey, [REDACTED]. If you would like to be involved, please complete the attached consent form (page 4) and return to [REDACTED] by [REDACTED]. I'll follow up on your email with potential dates that we could schedule an interview.

This study has been reviewed and approved by the UCL Institute of Education Research Ethics Committee (28 March 2022).

If you have any questions about the above research study, wish to exercise your rights as a research participant, or wish to make a complaint, please send an email with details to the UCL Institute of Education Research Ethics Committee on ioe.researchethics@ucl.ac.uk so that they can look into the issue and respond to you. You can also contact the UCL Institute of Education Research Ethics Committee by telephoning +44 (0) 207 911 5449.

Appendix iv. Consent Form

Study Title: Examining international leadership practices to promote a positive research culture in Higher Education Institutes.

	YES (Please Initial)	NO (Please Initial)
I have read and understood the Information Leaflet about this research study.		
I have been given the opportunity to ask questions about the study and my participation. I have received satisfactory answers to all questions asked and I am satisfied that I understand the information that I have received.		
I understand that I do not have to take part in this study and that I can opt out at any time. I understand that I do not have to give a reason for opting out and if I opt out, then any data I have contributed will not be used.		
I agree to the interview being recorded over Microsoft Teams or Zoom.		
I agree that the data I provide can be archived in a secure, cloud-based drive and will be deleted no more than twelve months following completion of the study.		
I understand that if any of my words are used in reports or presentations, they will not be attributed to me.		
I understand that upon completion of the interview and following sharing of my individualised interview transcript, I may choose to withdraw the information I have shared up to two weeks afterwards.		
I understand that my transcribed interview data will be analysed using NVivo.		
I understand that the results from this research study may be shared in peer-reviewed publications and/or conference presentations, and the final document of the research study will be published within the UCL research repository.		
I am aware of who to contact if I have queries/concerns about my involvement in this study.		

Signature of Research Participant: _____

Date: _____

To be completed by the Researcher/Person taking consent.

I, the undersigned, have taken the time to fully explain to the above participant the nature and purpose of this study in a way that they could understand. I have invited them to ask questions on any aspect of the study that concerned them. I have given them a copy of the information leaflet with my own contact information.

Signature of Researcher/Person taking consent: _____

Date: _____

Appendix v. Research Data Management Plan Plan Overview

A Data Management Plan created using DMPonline

Title: Examining international leadership practices to promote a positive research culture in Higher Education Institutes

Creator: Seán Lacey

Affiliation: University College London

Template: UCL data management plan template (all staff and research students)

Project abstract:

In Higher Education Institutes (HEIs) there is a growing emphasis on promoting good research practices in all aspects of research, from fundamental research to applied research to commercialisation. This study examines international leadership practices to promote a positive research culture in HEIs in terms of types of leadership models senior research leaders find are most effective, along with the practices they have found to be most impactful in leading change.

The research design was constructed using semi-structured interviews with five senior research leaders. Countries that were members of the European Network of Research Integrity Offices (ENRIO), with HEIs that were members of the European Association of Research Management and Administration (EARMA) were used as part of the sample selection process. With the topic being under-researched, the examination was kept as a small-scale exploratory study using opportunistic and purposive sampling to recruit participants. Data analysis was carried out using NVivo.

ID: 105706

Start date: 28-03-2022

End date: 12-09-2023

Last modified: 12-09-2022

Examining international leadership practices to promote a positive research culture in Higher Education Institutes

Study information

Brief description of research aims and objectives

The review of the literature has aided the development of the following research questions:

- Primary research question: What type of leadership models do senior research leaders find most effective in promoting a positive research culture in HEIs?
- Secondary research question: What practices have senior research leaders found most effective in leading change and promoting a positive research culture in their HEI, in line with changing internal and external requirements?

In parallel with the research questions, the following hypotheses will be tested:

1. Senior research leaders need to adapt their leadership style to respond to the regular changing of compliance and enhancement issues in HE research integrity.
2. Collective leadership is an appropriate approach to lead change to embed good research practices in the research culture.
3. In order to overcome leadership obstacles to promoting good research practices, the wider research community should be involved in policy and procedure development.

The study aims to address the above-mentioned research questions and hypotheses, with the aim of contributing to establishing evidence informed recommendations on leadership practices of research integrity to promote a positive research culture in HEIs, supported by existing literature.

Are you in receipt, or anticipate being in receipt, of external funding?

- no

Section 1: Collecting data and study materials

1.1 Are these digital or non-digital data / study materials?

1.2 Are these new data / study materials? Or do you plan on reusing and repurposing existing data / study materials? Briefly describe how you will collect or generate your data/ study materials

1.3 Describe the type(s) and format(s) of the data/study materials.

1.4 What is the anticipated volume of data or study materials?

1.5 Which steps will you take to ensure quality and reproducibility?

1.1 Digital data.

1.2 New data gathered for the purposes of a research study as part fulfilment of an MBA in Educational Leadership (International).

1.3 Voice recordings (*.mp3) and video recordings (*.mp4) stored as *.txt, transcribed, as *.docx and analysed in NVivo.

1.4 Five interviews in total, ranged in duration from 50 to 55 minutes

1.5 Transcripts shared with participants for accuracy and fairness, with consent from participants of same and for use in the research study.

Section 2: Storage, security and backup

2.1 Where will you store your data / study materials during your project?

2.2 What is the backup strategy for your storage platform/solution?

2.3 How will you secure your digital and non-digital items whilst they are: a) in transit; and b) when at UCL?

All data is stored on OneDrive.

Does your research involve living human participants?

- yes

As a core principle, educational research should do no harm and ideally benefit participants, researchers and the wider community, and should be carried out with integrity and honesty to participants throughout the research process (British Educational Research Association, 2018). Ethical issues raised with human participants include informed consent, respect for autonomy and confidentiality (British Educational Research Association, 2018). Furthermore, the research process

needs to be rigorous and impartial and executed to the highest possible standards so that it can contribute to the wider community and hence that the input from participants is not devalued. Participants' right to withdraw, along with the right to be debriefed at study end should always be ensured also.

Research ethical approval to start research on MBA dissertation received on 28 March 2022.

Informed consent form returned before commencing the interview

Study Title: Examining international leadership practices to promote a positive research culture in Higher Education Institutes.

	YES (Please Initial)	NO (Please Initial)
I have read and understood the Information Leaflet about this research study.		
I have been given the opportunity to ask questions about the study and my participation. I have received satisfactory answers to all questions asked and I am satisfied that I understand the information that I have received.		
I understand that I do not have to take part in this study and that I can opt out at any time. I understand that I do not have to give a reason for opting out and if I opt out, then any data I have contributed will not be used.		
I agree to the interview being recorded over Microsoft Teams or Zoom.		
I agree that the data I provide can be archived in a secure, cloud-based drive and will be deleted no more than twelve months following completion of the study.		
I understand that if any of my words are used in reports or presentations, they will not be attributed to me.		
I understand that upon completion of the interview and following sharing of my individualised interview transcript, I may choose to withdraw the information I have shared up to two weeks afterwards.		
I understand that my transcribed interview data will be analysed using NVivo.		
I understand that the results from this research study may be shared in peer-reviewed publications and/or conference presentations, and the final		

document of the research study will be published within the UCL research repository.		
I am aware of who to contact if I have queries/concerns about my involvement in this study.		

Signature of Research Participant: _____

Date: _____

To be completed by the Researcher/Person taking consent.

I, the undersigned, have taken the time to fully explain to the above participant the nature and purpose of this study in a way that they could understand. I have invited them to ask questions on any aspect of the study that concerned them. I have given them a copy of the information leaflet with my own contact information.

Signature of Researcher/Person taking consent: _____

Date: _____

Select one to describe your data / study materials

If you are not sure whether your data are sufficiently anonymised to not be subject to data protection legislation, select 'Not Sure' and an email will be sent to the Data Protection team who will contact you shortly.

- Fully anonymised

All data gathered will remain fully anonymised. The interview was designed so that it does not ask for any identifiable information. Responses in the interview were recorded for the purposes of transcription. Given the small purposive and opportunistic sampling approach, participants' names were recorded and instead interview participants are referred to as participant 1, 2, etc. Hence, data gathered is fully anonymous. Furthermore, in general, the reporting of the data is not concerned with individual responses as responses will be aggregated to deliver information organised by emerging themes. Where it is necessary to include quotes from individuals to support findings, quotes will be anonymised to ensure that the rights of that individual are respected and that the individual remains anonymous, with any specific identifying characteristics and personal data redacted. Participants received individualised interview transcript (with potential secondary identifiers removed) after the interview. Following sharing of the individualised interview transcript, participants had the right to withdraw the information. All participants approved transcripts for fairness and accuracy. At this point, the recordings were deleted, with the transcription stored securely for data analysis.

Section 3: Archiving, preservation and curation

11.1 Where do you plan on archiving your research outputs?

11.2 How long do you plan on preserving your research outputs for?

11.3 Does your intended archive/repository assign unique persistent identifiers such as a DOI?

11.4 How will you curate the data / study materials on a medium to longer-term basis?

Data is stored on One-Drive and in line with the Institute's Data Protection & Records Management Policy.

Data will be stored for one year after the completion of the dissertation and overall grade awarded to allow the possibility of dissemination at a conference and/or in peer-reviewed publication. After this point the data obtained (including transcripts imported into NVivo) will be destroyed in line with UCL's Records Retention Schedule for files relating to research data.

The final dissertation will be published within the UCL's institutional repository.

Will you need to destroy any data or study materials?

- yes

As agreed with participants through the Consent Form, the data will be archived in a secure, cloud-based drive and will be deleted no more than twelve months after the publication of the research.

Describe your plans for destroying your data / study materials including the reason(s) why?

Data will be overwritten (data wiped) with blank data on top of old transcript data. This process will erase the old material and render anything left blank. The NVivo project file will be deleted.

Section 4: Discovery, access and sharing

Which approaches will you take to make your research outputs discoverable?

The final dissertation will be published within UCL's institutional repository. The plan is to disseminate findings at conferences and in peer-reviewed open access publications.

Can you share your research outputs openly, or will you need to control or restrict access to these outputs for ethical, legal or commercial reasons?

- Yes - Research outputs can be made openly available

Section 5: Metadata - study documentation

17.1 Which metadata do you plan on creating and archiving as part of your research?

17.2 What format(s) do you plan on using to create your metadata?

17.3 What types of metadata do you plan on creating?

17.4 Will you use a metadata standard?

Given the research study is a small-scale exploratory study, excluding the sharing the dissertation on UCL's institutional repository (which includes appendices with Initial Interview Schedule; Ethics Approval Letter; Information Leaflet; Consent Form; Research Data Management Plan (as of 12 September 2022); RStudio Script for Figures generated; Word Frequency Analysis Tables; and Mapping of Codes to Themes) the intention is not to share/archive metadata.

Section 6: Rights and responsibilities

18.1 Who are the principal or lead investigators?

18.2 Who are the copyright owners?

18.3 Who is responsible for creating and maintaining metadata?

18.4 Who is responsible for ensuring compliance with any applicable legislation?

18.1 Jennifer J. Wilkinson (Supervisor)

18.2 Seán Lacey (Student)

18.3 Seán Lacey (Student)

18.4 Seán Lacey (Student)

Appendix vi. RStudio Script for Figures

Script for Figure 4.1

```
Cat<-c("A","B","C","D","E","F","G","H")
Value<-c(5,4,3,3,2,1,1,1)
df<-data.frame(Cat,Value)

fill <-
c("steelblue","gray79","cornflowerblue","cornflowerblue","gray59","deepskyblue","deepskyblue","deepskyblue")

library(ggplot2)
windows(20,10)
ggplot(df,aes(x=Cat,y=Value))+geom_bar(stat="identity",fill=fill,color="black")+theme_bw()+
  geom_text(aes(label=..Value..),vjust=-0.3,size=6.5)+
  theme(text = element_text(size=20))+labs(y="Number of participants", x="Good Research Practices")+
  scale_x_discrete(labels=c("A"="Discipline \nSpecific", "B"="Quality \nand \nTrustworthy",
    "C"="Openness \nand \nTransparency", "D"="Values \nBased",
    "E"="Legal \nObligations", "F"="Attribution",
    "G"="Policy \nand \nGuidelines", "H"="Valid \nand \nReliable"))
```

Script for Figure 4.4

```
library(ggplot2)
df <- data.frame(count=c(58, 53, 43, 36, 29, 24, 23),
  Themes=c("Leadership Practices and Culture Change", "Infrastructure, Training and Support in RI",
    "Research Misconduct, QRPs and Compliance",
    "External Engagements", "Reforming Research Assessment",
    "Research and Professional Development in RI", "Open Research Practices"))

df$Themes<-ordered(df$Themes,
  levels=c("Leadership Practices and Culture Change", "Infrastructure, Training and Support in RI",
    "Research Misconduct, QRPs and Compliance",
    "External Engagements", "Reforming Research Assessment",
    "Research and Professional Development in RI", "Open Research Practices"))

# Compute percentages
```

```

df$fraction = df$count / sum(df$count)
df = df[order(df$fraction), ]
# Compute the cumulative percentages (top of each rectangle)
df$ymax = cumsum(df$fraction)
# Compute the bottom of each rectangle
df$ymin = c(0, head(df$ymax, n=-1))

# select colours
fill <- c("steelblue", "gray79", "cornflowerblue", "gray59", "deepskyblue", "gray39", "lightskyblue")

windows(20,10)
(ggplot(df, aes(fill=Themes, ymax=ymax, ymin=ymin, xmax=4, xmin=3)) +
  scale_fill_manual(values=fill)+ geom_rect(colour="black") +
  coord_polar(theta="y") + xlim(c(0, 4)) + theme_void() +
  geom_label(aes(label = count,x = 3.5,y = (ymin + ymax) / 2),inherit.aes = TRUE,
  show.legend = FALSE,size=8)+
  theme(text = element_text(size=25))+
  theme(legend.spacing.y = unit(0.5, 'cm')) +
  guides(fill = guide_legend(byrow = TRUE)))

```

Appendix vii. Word Frequency Analysis Results

Table A.1 Initial word frequency analysis of most frequently occurring words, with a weighted percentage of at least 0.5%.

Word	Word Length	No. of Mentions	Weighted Percentage (%)	Similar Words
research	8	322	3.23	research, researcher, researchers, researchers', researches
people	6	123	1.23	people, peoples
institutions	12	94	0.94	institute, institutes, institution, institutional, institutionally, institutions
practices	9	69	0.69	practical, practice, practice', practices
integrity	9	64	0.64	integrated, integrating, integrity, integrity'
course	6	61	0.61	course, course', courses
different	9	55	0.55	difference, different, differently, differs

Table A.2 Word frequency analysis with stop-words approach implemented.

Word	Word Length	No. of Mentions	Weighted Percentage (%)	Similar Words
people	6	123	1.26	people, peoples
institutions	12	94	0.97	institute, institutes, institution, institutional, institutionally, institutions
practices	9	69	0.71	practical, practice, practice', practices
researchers	11	66	0.68	researcher, researchers, researchers', researches
integrity	9	64	0.66	integrated, integrating, integrity, integrity'
course	6	61	0.63	course, course', courses
different	9	55	0.57	difference, different, differently, differs
support	7	49	0.50	support, supporting, supportive

Appendix viii. Mapping of Codes to Themes

Table A.3 Mapping of collated codes, using axial coding, to overarching themes

Themes		Collated codes	
Label	No. of References	Label	No. of References
Leadership and Change Management	58	Attributes to Good Leadership	22
		Culture Change	22
		Consistency across Disciplines	14
Infrastructure, Training and Support in RI	53	Good Research Practice	20
		Training	12
		Capacity and Resources	9
		Awareness	6
		Supportive Environment	6
Research Misconduct, QRPs and Compliance	43	Policy and Procedures	14
		Internal Review	11
		Oversight and Supervision	10
		QRPs	5
		National Authority	3
External Engagements	36	External Agencies	19
		External Collaborations	17
Reforming Research Assessment	29	Research Assessment	17
		Incentive to Publish	6
		Research Metrics	4
		Incentive for Good Research Practices	2
Research and Professional Development in RI	24	Evidence-based and Co-created with Users	14
		Professional Learning	6
		Scholarship	4
Open Research Practices	23	Shared Learning Environment	9
		Open Communication	7
		Open Research Methods	5
		Disseminating	1
		Intellectual Property	1